

Homogeneous analysis of K2 multi-planet systems hosting Ultra Short Period planets

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Like all young men I set out to be
a genius, but mercifully laughter
intervened.

Lawrence Durrell, Clea.

Sospecho, sin embargo, que no
era muy capaz de pensar.

Jorge Luis Borges, Funes el
Memorioso.

If you hide your ignorance, no one
will hit you and you will never
learn.

Ray Bradbury, Fahrenheit 451.

He sido la desesperación de mis
maestros-repuso Batya-, pero al
final logré aprender algo.

Isaac Asimov, Fundación e
Imperio.

Abstract

Aims: Since the discovery of the first planet orbiting a star other than the Sun, a whole new area of Astrophysics was born. Several techniques for detecting exoplanets were developed. The two most successful are the Transit method and the Radial Velocity method. By combining both methods we are able to obtain radii and masses of exoplanets. This allow us to infer planet's composition and that give us information about planetary formation, migration, and evolution.

Methods: In this thesis we present an intensive analysis of public transit and radial velocity data. We used the scientific code `pyaneti` in order to perform a multi-planet transit and radial velocity analysis in order to derive planetary masses and radii.

Results: We derived the masses, radii and compositions of the exoplanets transiting the stars K2-106, K2-141 and HD 3167. Each of these stars hosts an Ultra Short Period (USP) planet accompanied with at least one outer planetary companion.

Conclusions: This thesis contributes to exoplanet community and increases our knowledge of the planetary parameters of the systems mentioned. Our characterisation represent an improvement in comparison with the previously reported in the scientific literature. This results will contribute to future developments in the study of USP planets.

Resumen

Objetivos: Con el descubrimiento del primer planeta en órbita alrededor de una estrella diferente Sol, nació una área completamente nueva de la Astrofísica. A partir de allí se desarrollaron varias técnicas para detectar exoplanetas. Las dos más exitosas son la técnica de tránsito y la de velocidad radial. Combinando ambos métodos podemos obtener radios y masas de exoplanetas. Esto nos permite inferir la composición del planeta y nos da información sobre la formación, migración y evolución planetaria.

Métodos: En esta tesis presentamos un análisis intensivo de datos públicos de tránsito y velocidad radial. Usamos el código científico `pyaneti` para realizar un análisis de tránsito de múltiples planetas y velocidad radial para derivar masas y radios planetarios.

Resultados: Derivamos las masas, radios y composiciones de los exoplanetas que transitan las estrellas K2-106, K2-141 y HD 3167. Cada una de estas estrellas alberga un planeta de período ultracorto (USP) acompañado de al menos un planeta con período más largo.

Conclusiones: Esta tesis contribuye a la comunidad de exoplanetas y aumenta nuestro conocimiento de los parámetros planetarios de los sistemas mencionados. Nuestra caracterización representa una mejora en comparación con lo reportado previamente en la literatura científica. Estos resultados contribuirán a futuros desarrollos en el estudio de los planetas de tipo USP.

Dedication

A Martita.

To Martha, my dear.

A Ilse, que me animó a entrar al posgrado y me presentó con Oscar. Esta tesis es tan suya como mía.

To Ilse, who encouraged me to enter graduate school and introduced me to Oscar. This thesis is as much hers as it is mine.

A Yosi, mi amor.

To Yosi, my love.

A Cano, Palito, Aldo, Adrián y Andrés.

To Cano, Palito, Erick, Aldo, Adrián y Andrés.

Para Aby, la más especial, que está en mi kokoro.

To Aby, my dearest one.

A Melis, por ayudarme a aplicar al doctorado en Francia.

To Melis, for helping me out in the application of the PhD at France.

Al Dr. Oscar Barragán y al Dr. Erick Nagel, por ser los mejores asesores del mundo y al posgrado en Astrofísica de la UG.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Mata su luz un fuego
abandonado.

Alejandra Pizarnik, Despedida.

1.1 Farewell to the dark sky

The International Astronomical Union confirms it: a growing majority of people can no longer see the beauty of the night sky from their homes. Even the brightest stars, like Sirius or Polaris, are completely gone. This problem includes, of course, the Milky Way as well. There are entire generations of people who have never seen our galaxy across the sky, the place we can call home in the Universe.

Astronomers define light pollution as “artificial light that shines where it is neither wanted, nor needed” ¹. The most important consequence of this kind of pollution is the increasing brightness of our night sky and subsequent difficulties in observing astronomical bodies from polluted locations. This is a serious problem that is affecting the whole world. For instance, 80% of world’s population live under light-polluted skies and more than 99% of the U.S. and European populations live under the same conditions, with the worst skies of them all being the ones above Qatar, Kuwait and Dubai (See [Falchi et al., 2016](#), p.3-5). In addition, there are also environmental problems because of light pollution. According to the Dark Sky International Association, light pollution disorient migratory birds leading them to deadly collisions ². There is also evidence that sea turtle hatchlings are attracted to artificial light once they are in the ocean. This behaviour is likely to subject them to greater risk of predation as [Thums et al. \(2016\)](#) have pointed out.

Probably the most recent and broadcasted problem regarding light pollution is related to one name: Elon Musk. Starlink, a mega constellation of internet satellites launched by Musk’s multimillionaire company SpaceX, is the new enemy for astronomers. With the promise of fast and cheap satellite internet for every part of the world, SpaceX has managed to launch thousands of small satellites into orbit. This would be a wonderful thing if it weren’t for a huge problem: Starlink satellites not only reflect enough sunlight to be easily seen at night even with the naked eye but emit radio signals

¹More details can be found in here: https://www.iau.org/public/themes/light_pollution/

²Other birds can become confused by artificial light, causing them to circle until dawn, leaving them weak when they land. A more detailed account of this problem can be found in here: <https://www.darksky.org/what-you-should-know-about-bird-migration-and-light-pollution/>

that can threaten radioastronomy. That's how Starlink satellites had ruin many astronomical observations since their first appearance in May 2019. Moreover, there are other companies willing to implement their own projects of mega constellations of satellites, like Amazon's Kuiper Systems or Facebook's Athena. Fortunately, several scientific and civil organisations have acted accordingly. International Astronomical Union (IAU), for instance, have created B7 commission³ in 2016. This commission was established in order to prevent artificial sky glow and radio interference. In 2019, IAU made a public statement⁴ expressing its support for a dark and radio-quiet sky and its concern regarding the growing number of satellites orbiting around the earth.

Light pollution has made even solar-system planets hard to recognise. The amazement caused by the bizarre movement across the sky of those five lights throughout the year, an amazement that even drove the ancient Greeks to name those strange lights as "wanderers", which is the original meaning for planets, is now almost completely lost. It would take a long time for mankind to come to an agreement about the nature of those faraway worlds. But with the knowledge about the existence of other planets, we changed our perception of what place we have in the Universe. Nevertheless, light pollution can destroy that change of perception, guiding us to a more primitive notion of ourselves.

1.2 A very brief History of Exoplanets

A complete and detailed history of the evolution of planetary studies along the history of science is out of the scope of this work. But this section will be, in Herman Melville's words, "a glancing bird's eye view" of the most remarkable scientific and philosophical achievements regarding exoplanets.

It is possible to track some clues about the existence of exoplanets within the origins of western culture. For instance, in a letter to his student Herodotus, Greek philosopher Epicurus stands that: "(...) the worlds are also infinite, whether they resemble this one of ours or whether they are different from it. For, as the atoms are, as to their number, infinite, as I have proved above (...) There is therefore, no fact inconsistent with an infinity of worlds. " (Yonge, 2017). Nevertheless, the colossal figure of Aristotle did much in overshadowing the work of the previous philosophers like Epicurus (See Stocks, 1922, Chapter 8). Aristotle's enormous influence persisted during the following fifteen centuries all along western culture.

Two Italians, Giordano Bruno and Galileo Galilei, are regarded as the first who created the "modern" conception of planetary science. Both were judged not only by the same severe catholic institution but by the same prelate: theologian and Cardinal Robert Bellarmine, the "Hammer of the Heretics". Bruno was the first of the two to be confronted by the catholic church due to his ideas. Most of those are present in the two books that he wrote: "The Ash Wednesday supper" and "On the infinite Universe and Worlds", both published in 1584 (Pogge, 2014). In those books, Bruno suggests using philosophical and theological arguments that distant stars are similar to our Sun. In fact he believed in an infinite number of stars with several planets orbiting each of those stars. In 1616 Bruno was finally burned alive in Florence due to his ideas. On the other hand, Galileo's fate was very different. In 1609, Galileo built a small telescope that allowed him to see with great detail the craters of the moon and four of the moons of Jupiter. These extraordinary discoveries were published in Galileo's most famous book "Starry Messenger". Of

³More details here: https://www.iau.org/science/scientific_bodies/commissions/B7/

⁴More details here: <https://www.iau.org/news/announcements/detail/ann19035/>

course, the discoveries were directly against the beliefs of catholic church regarding Earth's role in the Cosmos. In a historic attack, Cardinal Bellarmine used Psalms 93:1, 96:10, 104:5 and Ecclesiastes 1:5 in order to adjudicate the process between Galileo and Catholic Inquisition, a process now immensely famous and known as the *Galileo affair*. Nevertheless, Galileo was a close friend of Pope Paul V and his successor Urban VIII. This friendship allowed him to avoid death penalty and live the rest of his life under house arrest.

In XVIII century, Swedish scientist and theologian Emmanuel Swedenborg (whose work will be popularised much later by Jorge Luis Borges) proposed very radical ideas about the nature of the Universe. He believed, for instance, that the solar system, with the planets in it, was the result of the evolution of the same primordial structure. This implies that if stars formed in a similar way to the Sun, they may have planets as well. In fact, in a book called "Other planets" (Dole & Rose, 2018) Swedenborg wrote about the possible existence of planets whole around the Universe. In fact, he stated that planets "are bodies of physical matter (...) appear earthlike and (...) rotate on their axes as our planet does, which must cause days and the times of day called morning, afternoon, evening, and night. Not only that, some of them have moons called satellites" .

In XX century, Struve (1952) proposed a method for detecting exoplanets based on the variation of a star's radial velocity due to the presence of orbiting exoplanets. In the same article, Struve (1952) also proposed a method for detecting exoplanets based on transits. This article is regarded as the first paper to propose reliable methods for inferring the existence of exoplanets. The former method will be later known as the Radial Velocity (RV) method, and will be the key for the first detection of an exoplanet in the history of science.

In 1995, Mayor & Queloz (1995) detected for the first time a planet-mass companion to a main-sequence star, 51 Pegasi. Its planet companion would later be named 51 Pegasi b, which turns out to be a Jupiter-like planet, located very close to its host star. They detected the variations in the Radial Velocity of the star induced by the planet, as Struve (1952) proposed fifty years before. With this detection, achieved more than 2000 years since Epicurus, a whole new era of exoplanetary astronomy began. An era of huge accuracy spectrographs and transit space missions.

By October 1st, 2003, the High Accuracy Radial velocity Planet Searcher (HARPS) (Mayor et al., 2003) on ESO's 3.6 m telescope at La Silla Observatory, Chile, became operational. The instrument was built in order to obtain unprecedented high-long-term accuracy (on the order of 1 m s^{-1}) in radial velocity measurements. This accuracy constituted a revolution within exoplanetary community and marked the way up to the huge radial velocity precision nowadays. Details about radial velocity and why is so important for exoplanets community are given in Section 2.1.

If HARPS consisted a revolution for exoplanets community in terms of radial velocity precision, *Kepler* space mission was a revolution in terms of what space telescopes dedicated for detecting transits of exoplanets can achieve. The breakthrough began in March, 1st, 2007, when *Kepler* mission started its journey. This mission discovered thousands of transits of all kind of exoplanets (see e.g. Sanchis-Ojeda et al., 2014). However, *Kepler* lost two of its four reaction wheels and the space mission became eventually nonoperational. Then, and developed over the months following this failure, *K2* became fully operational in May 2014 to continue the legacy of *Kepler* mission. This mission provided hundred of transits around brighter stars than the observed by *Kepler* that allowed further characterisations. *K2* ended its operational mode in 2018, when it ran out of fuel.

Now, the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (*TESS*) space mission, launched in April 18, 2018, is currently operational and is the most important transiting space-based mission nowadays. This will change in the near future, with the arrival of *PLATO* and *ARIEL*.

The detection of presumably Earth-like planets in the habitable zone of their host stars is worth to mention. Since the discovery of 51 Pegasi b, finding Earth-like planets in the habitable zone of their host stars became a hope throughout time. In 2011, [Schulze-Makuch et al. \(2011\)](#) created a very interesting and useful scale for this subject. The Earth-Similarity-index (ESI), or “easy scale”, is an open multi-parameter measure of Earth-likeness for exoplanets. The ESI scale is presented as a number between zero (no similarity) and one (identical to Earth). The ESI scale is based on data available or potentially available of most exoplanets, such as mass, radius, and temperature. At the last update (July 30th, 2021) of the website⁵ of the Planetary Habitability Laboratory of University of Puerto Rico at Arecibo, it is shown a total of 60 exoplanets potentially habitable nowadays. However, the detection of a second Earth has elude us.

1.3 What is an exoplanet and how do we classify them?

1.3.1 Definition of planet and exoplanet

The latest and in fact, first, definition of “planet” was established in 2006 at the IAU assembly. According to their resolutions B5 and B6⁶, a solar system body is a planet if and only if fulfils the three following requirements:

1. It orbits around the Sun.
2. It has sufficient mass for its self-gravity to overcome rigid body forces so that it assumes a hydrostatic equilibrium (nearly round) shape.
3. It has cleared the neighbourhood around its orbit.

Therefore, there are eight planets in our solar system: the Earth, then the five planets that can be seen with the naked eye (Mercury, Venus, Mars, Jupiter and Saturn) and finally the two planets discovered using telescopes (Neptune and Uranus).

It is necessary to generalise the definition already mentioned in order to define exoplanets in a rigorous way. This was done in 2018 by the IAU commission F2⁷. They proposed a brand new definition of planet in order to include exoplanets. The new resolution defines exoplanets as follows:

- Objects with true masses below the limiting mass for thermonuclear fusion of deuterium (currently estimated to be 13 Jupiter masses for objects of solar metallicity) that orbit stars, brown dwarfs, or stellar remnants and that have a mass ratio q with the central object below the $L4/L5$ instability ($q < 2/(25 + \sqrt{521}) \sim 1/25$) are “planets” no matter how they formed.
- The minimum mass/size required for an extrasolar object to be considered a planet should be the same as that used in our Solar System.
- We can expect this definition to evolve as our knowledge improves.

⁵See: <http://phl.upr.edu/projects/habitable-exoplanets-catalog>

⁶See: https://www.iau.org/static/resolutions/Resolution_GA26-5-6.pdf

⁷See: https://www.iau.org/science/scientific_bodies/commissions/F2/info/documents/

1.3.2 Nomenclature of exoplanets

The nomenclature for naming exoplanets usually consists in two elements: a noun or abbreviation and then a lower case letter.⁸

The noun can be taken from different sources. A common one is the name of the exoplanet's host star. For this case there are two options: First, if the star has a widely recognised name, then that name can be used as the proper noun. Second, if the name of the host star is not widely recognised, then its identification inside some important catalog can be used. In this catalog, exoplanets are identified first by the space mission or project that discovered them (such as WASP-, CoRoT-, Kepler- or K2-), followed by the coordinate that locate them in space. However, it is recommended (by IAU) to use stellar names already in existing catalogs (such as HD or GJ).

The first exoplanet discovered in a stellar system is designated with the lower case letter *b*, the second planet discovered will have a *c*, the third will have a *d* and so on. It is very important to state that the lower case letter does not indicate the planet's orbital placement around its host star. This means that, for instance, exoplanet-c could be closer to its host star than exoplanet-b.

1.4 Planetary Mass and Radius

Planetary masses and radii are parameters needed to characterise the physical properties of exoplanets. The number of discovered exoplanets is continuously increasing. As of today, Feb. 9, 2021 there are 4301 exoplanets confirmed. However, the number of exoplanets with mass and radius measurements is comparatively very low, only 993.⁹ To understand the variety of chemical composition of exoplanetary systems, we can study their mass-radius relation. An example of a mass-radius diagram for exoplanets is shown in Fig. 1.1a. This Figure shows the planetary population of exoplanets with mass and radius measured with more than 30 % uncertainty. We can see that the population of discovered exoplanet covers a wide range of masses and radii, ranging from planets in the Earth size-mass domain (very few) to the Jupiter-like regime. Figure 1.1b shows an example of how mass-radius diagrams can be interpreted in terms of different planet compositions. It shows also different theoretical composition models from Zeng et al. (2016). The different models are identified by different colour lines, related to the different mass-radius relations predicted by this models. These correspond to interior of planets formed of two layers (a solid core and an envelope) that combine different fractions of iron (*Fe*), silicates (*MgSiO₃*) and water (*H₂O*). By comparing the position of an exoplanet (for which both, mass and radius measurements are available) on this diagram, it is possible to have a first order approximation of its composition.

However, if the uncertainties of the measurements are too high, then identifying the solution becomes degenerated. Figure 1.1b also shows three fictitious planets where the uncertainties go from good to worst (from left to right). Even if the values of the three fictitious planets follows the same model, the uncertainties do not allow to infer the planet composition. Therefore, reducing the uncertainties on the measurements of planetary radii and masses is crucial.

⁸A very detailed account of how to name exoplanets can be found in the following link: <https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/docs/K2Numbers.html> Also, there is a very interesting section in that website regarding what NOT to do when naming exoplanets.

⁹As of February 9th, 2021. These and more values regarding exoplanets can be found in here: https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/docs/counts_detail.html

(a) Mass-Radius diagram for exoplanets with radius and mass measured with more than 30% uncertainty. Both axes are in logarithmic scale. The Earth, Neptune, and Jupiter are shown in the diagram to help the reader to localise mass and radius ranges. Data taken from the TEPICAT data base (Southworth, 2011).

(b) Mass-Radius diagram with composition lines for small-mass exoplanets (Zeng et al., 2016). The green points are three fictitious exoplanets with the same interior composition, but different mass and radius error bars.

Figure 1.1: Examples of mass-radius diagrams for exoplanets.

1.5 Detection methods

In this thesis we will only concentrate on the two most successful methods for exoplanetary detection: the radial velocity (RV) method and (Tr) transit method. It is important to mention that these are not the only methods for detecting exoplanets. Other methods are, for instance, direct imaging (Cantalloube et al., 2021), pulsar timing (Wolszczan & Frail, 1992), microlensing (Tsapras, 2018), bright modulation (Guyon et al., 2010), astrometry (Xu et al., 2017) among others. It is notable that out of the 4301 exoplanets known to date¹⁰, 4129 have been detected via RV and Transit methods together. Fig. 1.2 shows the planet mass vs orbital period plot. The different colours/symbols refer to the different detection methods.

¹⁰As of Feb. 9, 2021, <https://exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu/>

Figure 1.2: In this Planet mass-orbital period diagram different colours/symbols refer to a different discovery technique. The figure was created with data downloaded from exoplanetarchive.ipac.caltech.edu, as of February 9th, 2021. A code I wrote myself showing how this kind of plot can be made using python library pandas can be found in my github page.

1.6 The radius valley for small planets

One of the most exciting discoveries of the last years is that there is a dichotomy on the radius distribution for small ($< 4R_{\oplus}$), short period ($< 100\text{d}$) planets, where R_{\oplus} stands for 1 Earth radius. [Fulton et al. \(2017\)](#) discovered that there is a gap that splits small planets into two size regimes, $R_p < 1.5R_{\oplus}$ and $R_p = (2 - 4) R_{\oplus}$.

Figure 1.3 shows the radius valley as it was found by [Fulton et al. \(2017\)](#). This radius valley has been confirmed by different authors using different methods and data sets (e.g., [Van Eylen et al., 2018](#)). This valley is not an observational bias. The reason for this is the following: if we have already seen smaller and bigger planets than the ones that should be on the gap, then there is no reason to believe in any observational bias causing the radius valley. This lack of planets between 1.5 and 2.0 R_{\oplus} is crucial to understand the composition, migration, and formation mechanisms that shape sub-Neptune sized worlds. If we want to understand more about the nature of this bi-modality, planetary radii are not enough, we need to know the masses, and other physical and orbital parameters of planets that lie in both sides of the valley. In order to understand better the radius valley, we need an homogeneous sample of masses and radii of planets located on both side of the valley with the best precision possible.

Figure 1.3: Histogram of planet radii for planets with orbital periods shorter than 100 days, as observed by [Fulton et al. \(2017\)](#). A lack of planets between 1.5 and 2.0 R_{\oplus} is visible. The light gray region of the histogram for radii smaller than 1.14 R_{\oplus} suffers from low completeness.

1.7 Ultra Short Period Planets

Interestingly, the radius valley was predicted previously by modellers (e.g., [Owen & Wu, 2013](#)). Stellar irradiance on small planets play a major role in explaining some of the observed diversity in small planet radii. Photo-evaporation can strip the atmosphere of a Neptune-like planet leaving behind a dense rocky core. In this context, small planets with orbital periods shorter than one Earth day, also called Ultra-Short Period (USP) planets, may be important objects in understanding the role of photo-evaporation. Given the proximity to their host stars, USP planets are expected to be stripped cores of planets that have lost their atmospheres due to photo-evaporation. In fact, most of the USP planets found by the *Kepler* mission have $R_p < 1.7R_{\oplus}$ ([Sanchis-Ojeda et al., 2014](#)), i.e., they all lie on the small radius side of the radius valley.

The interest in USP planets have been growing in recent years. They have been one of the most studied topics lately for the exoplanet community. This allows better determination of the characteristics of USP planets. For instance, we know that all known USP planets do not have the same size. Among them there are Jupiter-size giants planets and small terrestrial planets (see e.g. [Huang & Ji, 2020](#)). We also know that USPs are not alone in their systems. Typically, they have outer planetary companions with periods ranging from a few to tens of days (e.g. [Adams et al., 2017](#); [Vanderburg et al., 2016](#)). When the outer companions have been found transiting, their sizes are typically $> 2R_{\oplus}$, i.e., they lie on the second side of the radius valley.

Recent studies have shown that USP planets have a high density, consistent with a composition made of different mixtures of silicates and metals, with insignificant envelope (see e.g. [Dai et al., 2021](#)). It also seems that all the USP planets tend to orbit solar-like metallicity stars, according to [Winn et al. \(2017\)](#). While their outer companions have significantly lower density, consistent with planets formed by a heavy core and a significant volatile envelope (see e.g. [Gandolfi et al., 2017](#); [Guenther et al., 2017](#)). These results are consistent with photo-evaporation models that predict that USPs will lose their atmosphere due to high stellar irradiation, while the less irradiated companions can maintain their atmosphere. This implies that better measuring the masses and

radii of planets in multi-planet systems hosting USP planets offer the opportunity for testing the hypothesis of photo-evaporation.

1.8 Objective of this thesis

The aim of this thesis is to perform a homogeneous analysis, in terms of planet mass and radius determination for multi-planet systems hosting USP planets. This will make it possible to study: first, if the bulk composition of the USP planets are consistent between them; second, the fact that they are in multiple systems will allow us to search for similitude or differences between the planets with longer orbits. These results will give us clues on the formation and physical mechanism that shape such worlds. In this thesis, the following systems will be analyzed: *K2*-106, *K2*-141 and HD 3167. All these systems have at least two transiting planets, where the innermost planet is a USP planet. Below a brief description of these systems can be found:

- **K2-106**: was discovered and validated as a planetary system by [Adams et al. \(2017\)](#). The system host two planets: K2-106 b that is a USP planet and its outer companion K2-106 c with a longer period. Both planets have been confirmed with a mass measurement independently by [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#). In this thesis we will use both data sets for our analyses. We expect that this will allow us to determine the masses with lower uncertainty.
- **K2-141**: was studied independently by [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#). [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) measured the mass of *K2*-141 b and identified it as an USP planet. [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#) also observed *K2*-141 b and detected an extra transiting companion called *K2*-141 c but were not able to determine its mass. In this work we will combine the two RV data sets provided by both teams and we will determine the mass of K2-141 c. We will also analyse new data provided by the *K2* mission that were released after both works were published, which we expect should improve the radius measurement of the planets.
- **HD 3167**: was discovered and validated as a planetary system by [Vanderburg et al. \(2016\)](#). Later, [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#) measured the mass of HD 3167 b and HD 3167 c. With a larger data set, [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) found similar results, plus an extra RV signal that they published as a new planet labelled HD 3167 d. We will combine the RV datasets provided by both teams. We expect to get better estimate for the mass. We will also determine whether the signal observed by [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) is indeed of planetary origin.

In a few words, the objective of this thesis is: **To combine all the publicly-available transit photometry and RV time-series to improve the masses and radii measurements of the planets in the three planetary systems: K2-106, K2-141, and HD 3167.**

Chapter 2

Radial Velocity and Transit Equations

Lo bueno, si breve, dos veces
bueno

Baltasar Gracián, Oráculo
manual y arte de prudencia.

In this chapter we present and describe both RV and Transit methods for discovering exoplanets. First, we show the most important RV equations for detecting exoplanets and then we show the most important Transit equations. We also show the importance about taking into account whether or not a star is a uniform source of light. Finally, we present the most important applications of both RV and Transit methods.

2.1 Radial Velocity Method

The RV method for detecting exoplanets is based on the following physical scenario: When a star is hosting a planetary system, the gravitational interaction between them is mutual. This interaction causes star and planets to orbit the center of mass of the system. This point is also called the barycenter of the system. The motion of the star around the barycenter of the system can be seen as a change in its radial velocity. The radial velocity of a star is the velocity of the star projected onto the line-of-sight. This change causes the spectral lines of the star to get Doppler shifted. Measuring that shift, $\Delta\lambda$, allows us to determine the change of the star's radial velocity caused by the planetary system. With RV measurements it is possible to determine orbital parameters such as the period or eccentricity. But if we want to measure the mass of a planet, the RV method alone is not enough (See [Keeton, 2014](#), p.67-70). Therefore, RV measurements can only be used to calculate the *planet minimum mass*, which is the planet true mass multiplied by the sine of the orbital inclination, which cannot be obtained via the RV method.

2.2 Radial Velocity Equations

A detailed derivation of RV equations can be found in [Murray & Correia \(2010\)](#). In this section I will show only the most important equations. The radial velocity changes of a star orbited by a

single planet are described by

$$v_r = v_z + K [\cos(\omega_* + \nu) + e \cos \omega_*] \quad (2.1)$$

In eq.(2.1) there is an implicit, but crucial, dependence on time. The time dependence is present in the so-called true anomaly, $\nu = \nu(t)$. The true anomaly ν is a function of the periastron passage time T_p , the orbital period P , the orbital eccentricity e , and time. The other parameters in eq.(2.1) are the following: v_z is the proper motion of the barycenter along the line of sight, e is star's orbit eccentricity around the barycenter, ω_* is an angle called the argument of periastron of the star and, finally K is the Doppler semi-amplitude or RV semi-amplitude, which is defined as

$$K \equiv \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \frac{2\pi a_1}{P\sqrt{1-e^2}} \sin i, \quad (2.2)$$

where P is the orbital period, i is the orbital inclination, m_1 is the mass of the star, m_2 is the mass of the planet and a_1 is a scaled semi-major axis defined as

$$a_1 = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2} a, \quad (2.3)$$

where a is the semi-major axis of the planet. Equation (2.2) relates K with the other orbital parameters and masses of both bodies and it can be rewritten as (see Murray & Correia, 2010)

$$K = \left(\frac{2\pi G}{P}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \frac{m_2}{(m_2 + m_1)^{\frac{2}{3}}} \frac{1}{(1-e^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin i, \quad (2.4)$$

where it can be seen that the dependence on a is eliminated. In addition, eq. (2.4) depends on the orbital inclination i , that cannot be determined from RV observations. If we can measure the stellar mass with an independent method (spectroscopy or asteroseismology), eq. (2.4) provides the planet mass multiplied by $\sin i$, which is the planet minimum mass.

2.2.1 Planet minimum mass

Given that eq. (2.4) is transcendental in terms of m_2 , there are two approaches to calculate the planet minimum mass. The first consists in assuming $m_1 \gg m_2$, which implies that $m_2 + m_1 \approx m_1$ and that eq. (2.2) can be rewritten as

$$m_2 \sin i \sim K \left(\frac{2\pi G}{P}\right)^{-\frac{1}{3}} m_1^{\frac{2}{3}} \sqrt{1-e^2}. \quad (2.5)$$

Equation (2.5) can be solved analytically.

The second approach consists in defining the function

$$f(m_2) = \left(\frac{2\pi G}{P}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \frac{m_2}{(m_2 + m_1)^{\frac{2}{3}}} \frac{1}{(1-e^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sin(i) - K. \quad (2.6)$$

This equation can be solved by using iterative numerical methods (such as Newton-Raphson) to find the solution for m_2 . We note that this method does not assume $m_1 \gg m_2$.

However, in order to obtain the *planet true mass*, m_2 , the orbital inclination i has to be known. This is what the transit method is useful for.

2.2.2 Multi-planet case.

When a star is being orbited by N_p planets there is no analytical solution that describes the stellar motion. However, a reasonable assumption is that the planet-planet interaction is negligible, implying that each planet pull the star independently. Therefore, the subsequent Doppler reflex motion induced by each small mass can be solved independently assuming Keplerian orbits. By adopting this assumption, the general expression for eq. (2.1) becomes

$$v_r = v_z + \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} K_j [\cos(\nu_j + \omega_{*,j}) + e_j \cos \omega_{*,j}] \quad (2.7)$$

Where each planet j has its own set of physical parameters $\{T_{0,j}, P_j, e_j, \omega_{*,j}, K_j\}$.

2.3 Transit Method

The transit method could be understood in terms of the eclipse phenomenon. An eclipse occurs when an astronomical body is totally obscured by another passing right in our line of sight. A *transit* is just a special case of an eclipse, happening when a very small object passes in front of a larger body. If the orbit inclination is close to 90° , the presence of a planet orbiting its host star can be inferred by detecting the periodic drops of stellar flux caused by the planet partly occulting the stellar disc.

If the radius and distance from the star is known through, e.g., spectroscopy combined with parallax, the Tr method allows us to determine the radius of the exoplanets. This is because the fraction of light occulted by a planet during a transit is indeed proportional to its size. For instance, for a Jupiter-like exoplanet orbiting a Solar-like star, the transit of that planet would occult 1% of the star's light.

According to Collier Cameron (2016), if we assume a completely random inclination of planetary orbits, the probability of a transit to happen goes as $\sim 0.0046 (R_*/R_\odot) (1AU/a)$, where R_* is the host star radius and a is the semi-major axis of the orbit of the planet. This implies that the probability of observing the transit of an Earth-like planet with $a = 1AU$ is only 0.46%. On the other hand, for a Jupiter-like planet with $a = 5.2AU$, the probability drops to 0.009%. For shorter period exoplanets ($P < 10d$), the transit probability ranges between 2 and 10%.

2.4 Transit Equations

We have described how the presence of a planet orbiting its host star can be inferred by detecting the periodic drops of stellar flux observed when the planet is transiting its host star. An useful quantity to describe planetary transits is the scaled projected distance in the sky (plane X-Y) between the planet and star centers. Following Eastman et al. (2010) this distance can be written as

$$\delta = \frac{a}{R_*} \frac{1 - e^2}{1 + e \cos \nu} \sqrt{1 - \sin^2(\nu + \omega_*) \sin^2 i} \quad (2.8)$$

where a is the semi-major axis, R_* is radius of the star, e is the orbital eccentricity, ν is the true anomaly, ω_* is the angle of periastron and i is the orbital inclination. If we define now

$$r_p \equiv \frac{R_p}{R_*} \quad (2.9)$$

as the planet-to-star radius ratio, we can use eq. (2.8) to show that a transit occurs only when $\delta < 1 + r_p$ and $\sin(\nu + \omega_*) > 0$ (star behind the planet). On the other hand, an occultation, or secondary eclipse, only occurs when $\delta < 1 + r_p$ and $\sin(\nu + \omega_*) < 0$ (planet behind the star).

In order to analytically describe how the total flux $F(t)$ changes as a function of time due to the presence of a transiting planet, we need to account for the disc-integrated stellar flux $F_*(t)$, the planet flux $F_p(t)$ (both, reflected light and thermal emission), and the loss of light when transits/occultations occur $\lambda(\delta, r_p)$. The total flux $F(t)$ is given by

$$F(t) = F_*(t) + F_p(t) - \lambda(\delta, r_p) \quad (2.10)$$

We will assume that we observe the flux relative to the stellar flux, therefore $F_*(t) = 1$. We also assume that the planet contribution to the flux is negligible, i.e. $F_p = 0$. With that in mind, eq.(2.10) can be written as

$$F(t) = 1 - \lambda(\delta, r_p) \quad (2.11)$$

2.4.1 Stars as uniform sources of light

As a first approximation, stars can be modelled as uniform sources of light (Seager & Mallen-Ornelas, 2003). It is possible to describe stellar flux with a constant function $I = I_0$. According to Mandel & Agol (2002) the analytical description of λ is

$$\lambda(\delta, r_p) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \delta > 1 + r_p \\ \frac{1}{\pi} \left[r_p^2 \kappa_0 + \kappa_1 - \sqrt{\frac{4\delta^2 - (1 + \delta^2 - r_p^2)^2}{4}} \right] & \text{if } 1 - r_p < \delta < 1 + r_p \\ r_p^2 & \text{if } \delta < 1 - r_p \end{cases} \quad (2.12)$$

Where $\kappa_0 = \cos^{-1} [(r_p^2 + \delta^2 - 1)/(2r_p\delta)]$ and $\kappa_1 = \cos^{-1} [(1 - r_p^2 + \delta^2)/(2\delta)]$. What eq. (2.12) tells us is: 1) when $\delta > 1 + r_p$, the planet does not occult the stellar disc, then $\lambda = 0$; 2) when $1 - r_p < \delta < 1 + r_p$ between the transit ingress and egress the light decreases and increases continuously; 3) when $\delta < 1 - r_p$ the planet's disc is entirely in front of the stellar disc, the loss of flux is constant and equal to the planet-to-star area ratio, $r_p^2 = (R_p/R_*)^2$.

2.4.2 Stars as non-uniform sources of light

Stars are not uniform sources of light in reality. Several phenomena prevent stars to be characterized that way. For instance, variations in temperature and opacity make them look brighter in the center but fainter at the edge or limb, this is what we call *limb darkening* (see e.g. Claret & Bloemen, 2011). More precisely, the local temperature in the atmosphere increases with depth and the radiation leaving the star comes from layers with a lower optical depth. The layers responsible for this radiation are hotter in the center than near the limb. The effective temperature of the photosphere also decreases with increasing distance from the center of the star. The radiation emitted from a gas is approximately black-body radiation, the intensity of which is proportional to the fourth power of the temperature. Therefore, even in line of sight directions where the optical depth is effectively infinite, the emitted energy comes from cooler parts of the photosphere, resulting in less total energy reaching the viewer. This effect is very important when dealing with transit light curves. Limb darkening has to be taken into account because it changes the observed stellar flux when a planet passes in front of its host star. For instance, a larger flux decrease is

observed when the planet transits close to the star center than near the edge.

Limb darkening effects can be characterized by parametrizing the intensity of the stellar disc I . For instance, we can assume $I = I(\mu)$ where $\mu = \cos\theta$ and θ is the angle between the line of sight and the normal to a given point of the surface. Some of the most widely-used limb darkening laws in exoplanet transit light-curve fitting are given by linear, logarithmic or exponential equations (see e.g. Claret & Hauschildt, 2003; Espinoza & Jordán, 2015). In this work we adopt the quadratic limb darkening model as described by Mandel & Agol (2002).

2.4.3 Multiple transiting exoplanets

Systems where there are more than one transiting exoplanet definitively exist (see e.g. Grimm et al., 2018; Rodriguez et al., 2018). For a system where N_p planets transit, the relative flux of the star becomes

$$F(t) = 1 - \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \lambda_j(\delta, r_p) \quad (2.13)$$

It is important to mention that when using eq. (2.13) we are not taking into account occultations between planets.

2.5 Science with RV and Transit methods

2.5.1 Science with the transit method

Planet equilibrium temperature and insolation

Transit method can reveal the existence of planets when they pass in front of the stars. Seager & Mallen-Ornelas (2003) showed that in the case of a planet on a circular orbit around a star considered as a uniform source of light, there are analytical relations that can be used to obtain the orbital parameters of the system. However, in more realistic cases, orbits are not circular and stars have limb darkening. This is why we need to compare the data with theoretical models to estimate the planetary parameters. Once those parameters are estimated and if we have an estimation of the stellar temperature, T_* , we can compute the planet equilibrium temperature as

$$T_{\text{eq}} = T_* (1 - \alpha)^{\frac{1}{4}} \sqrt{\frac{R_*}{2a}} \quad (2.14)$$

Where α is the planet *albedo*. We can also estimate the insolation received by a planet as

$$F_p = \left(\frac{R_*}{R_{\odot}}\right)^2 \left(\frac{T_*}{T_{\odot}}\right)^4 \left(\frac{AU}{a}\right)^2 F_{\oplus} \quad (2.15)$$

where F_{\oplus} is the insolation flux received by Earth. Determining F_p for USP planets and companions is essential to test the evaporation hypothesis.

Stellar density

One of the most interesting facts about transit method is that it provides a way to calculate the stellar mean density of the host star. In order to do that we need Kepler's third law expression of planetary motion. Applying Kepler's third law and considering the stellar volume of the star, $V_* = (4/3)\pi R_*^3$, we obtain

$$\rho_* + \left(\frac{R_p}{R_*}\right)^3 \rho_p = \frac{3\pi}{G} \frac{1}{P^2} \left(\frac{a}{R_*}\right)^3 \quad (2.16)$$

where ρ_* and ρ_p are the stellar and planetary densities, respectively. Because the term $(R_p/R_*)^3$ is very small it can be neglected. This gives

$$\rho_* \sim \frac{3\pi}{G} \frac{1}{P^2} \left(\frac{a}{R_*}\right)^3 \quad (2.17)$$

Eq. (2.17) can be used as a comparative tool. We can compare the value of ρ_* obtained with the transit method and the ρ_* derived from spectroscopic measurements. With this comparison we can use transit light curves to better constrain the fundamental parameters of the host star (see e.g., [Sozzetti et al., 2007](#)). Also, transiting targets are particularly suited for atmospheric characterization (the interested reader can visit this recent review of [Madhusudhan, 2019](#), for more details).

2.5.2 Science with RV and transit methods

Planet surface gravity

With transit and RV measurements we can obtain the necessary parameters to estimate the planet surface gravity. According to [Southworth et al. \(2007\)](#), this can be done as follows

$$g_p = \frac{2\pi}{P} \frac{\sqrt{1-e^2} K}{R_p^2/a^2 \sin i} \quad (2.18)$$

The surface gravity can also be derived as follows

$$g_p = \frac{Gm_2}{R_p^2} \quad (2.19)$$

where m_2 is the mass of the planet and R_p is the planet radius calculated assuming a given set of stellar parameters. We can compare the two estimates of the gravity derived using equations (2.18) and (2.19) to verify that stellar parameters have been derived correctly.

Chapter 3

From Data to Exoplanets

Pensar es estar enfermo de los
ojos

Fernando Pessoa, El guardador de
rebaños.

In this chapter we first give a very brief presentation of some of the most important instruments for this thesis. The first instrument that we show is the *K2* space mission. Then, we present a brief description of the high-resolution spectrographs: FIES, HARPS and HARPS-N. After this, we present a concise recap of Bayesian analyses and MCMC algorithms. Finally, we present `pyaneti` to the reader and give some technical details about it.

3.1 The K2 space mission

After reaction wheels of *Kepler* space mission became unoperational, in 2014, *Kepler* project team proposed a new mission concept named *K2* (Howell et al., 2014). The *K2* mission involved a series of sequential observing Campaigns distributed around the ecliptic plane and offered a photometric precision approaching that of the original *Kepler* mission. Operating in the ecliptic plane minimises the torque exerted on the spacecraft by solar wind pressure, reducing pointing drift to the point where spacecraft attitude can effectively be controlled through a combination of thrusters and the two remaining reaction wheels. Each campaign was therefore limited by Sun angle constraints to a duration of approximately 80 days, observing towards the same sky region in the ecliptic plane.

K2 focused on stars brighter than the ones *Kepler* mission observed ($V \leq 13$). This means that transiting exoplanets detected around the bright stars observed by *K2* could be monitored with ground-based instruments (i.e. high-precision spectrographs) more easily. Also, bright stars can be characterised better than faint ones. Therefore, *K2* space mission allowed precise stellar characterisations.

3.2 Some High-Resolution Spectrographs

3.2.1 FIES

The Fibre-fed Echelle Spectrograph (FIES Frandsen & Lindberg, 1999; Telting et al., 2014) is mounted at the 2.56 m Nordic Optical Telescope, which is located at the *Roque de los Muchachos* observatory in the Canary Island of *La Palma* (Spain). The spectrograph is fed by an octagonal

fibre. FIES has a high efficiency and can reach an RV precision of less than $2 - 3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The spectra are reduced using standard procedures specifically designed for Echelle spectrographs. The radial velocity measurements are derived via multi-order cross-correlation with the spectrum of an RV standard star observed with the same instrument set-up as the target of interest.

3.2.2 HARPS

The High Accuracy Radial velocity Planet Searcher spectrograph [Mayor et al. \(2003\)](#) is mounted at the ESO-3.6 m telescope at La Silla observatory (Chile). The instrument is a fibre-fed cross-dispersed Echelle spectrograph. HARPS is kept in vacuum with a pressure always below 0.01 mbar. This ensures that the daily instrument RV drift is well below 1 m s^{-1} . The RV measurements are measured by cross-correlating the observed spectra with numerical masks.

3.2.3 HARPS-N

The HARPS-N spectrograph [Cosentino et al. \(2012\)](#) is mounted at the 3.6 m Telescopio Nazionale Galileo (TNG) of Roque de los Muchachos Observatory (La Palma island, Spain). HARPS-N is a copy of the HARPS spectrograph. It has been designed to be the most precise spectrograph in the Northern hemisphere. The instrument characteristics, including the achieved RV stability, spectral resolution, and spectral coverage, are very similar to those of HARPS. The HARPS-N data are reduced using a dedicated HARPS-N pipeline. Radial velocities are extracted by cross-correlating the observed spectra with numerical masks.

3.3 Bayesian Statistics

The aim of data analysis is to extract information from experiments and/or observations. In this project, we are interested in extracting planetary physical parameters by comparing time-dependent parametric models with astronomical observations. In probabilistic terms, we are interested in estimating the probability for a parametric model $M = M(\vec{\phi})$ to explain the data, D . In terms of Bayes' theorem, this is called the conditional probability of M given D and it is written as $P(M|D)$.

Bayes' theorem ([Bayes & Price, 1763](#)) has been a cornerstone in Probability and Statistics. This theorem provides a robust framework when it comes to obtain the probability that a certain model is consistent with the data, which is the joint posterior distribution $P(M|D)$

$$P(M|D) = \frac{P(D|M)P(M)}{P(D)} \quad (3.1)$$

In eq. (3.1) $P(D|M)$ is a function called the *Likelihood* of observing the dataset D when the model M is true. On the other hand, $P(M)$ is called the *Prior* model probability which is based on our prior knowledge about the model M being true. Finally, $P(D)$ it is called *evidence*.

3.3.1 Likelihood

Let D be a dataset with N elements (D_1, D_2, \dots, D_N) . For each datum of D we can generate a predicted point from our model M , so that we can have N predicted points (M_1, M_2, \dots, M_N) as well. The likelihood of a data point D_i being described by a point M_i is $P(D_i|M_i)$. Assuming the probabilities are statistically independent, the likelihood of the whole data set D to be described by the model M is given by the product of each probability $P(D_i|M_i)$ as follows

$$P(D|M) = \prod_{n=1}^N P(D_i|M_i) \quad (3.2)$$

In order to compute $P(D|M)$, we need to find out which likelihood function best describes our dataset. If we assume that our measurements are normally-distributed and that only contain uncorrelated noise σ_i , the likelihood of the data point D_i being true, assuming M_i is also true, is written as

$$P(D_i|M_i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi(\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_j^2)}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(D_i - M_i)^2}{\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_j^2}\right\} \quad (3.3)$$

Where the terms σ_j (often called *jitter terms*) are used to normalize the likelihood in the case the nominal uncertainties σ_i are underestimated (see e.g., [Sharma, 2017](#)). If we use eq. (3.3) to calculate the likelihood for all the dataset D we obtain:

$$P(D|M) = \prod_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi(\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_j^2)}} \right] \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}\chi^2\right\} \quad (3.4)$$

Where

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(D_i - M_i)^2}{\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_j^2} \quad (3.5)$$

is the *chi square* function, χ^2 .

3.3.2 Priors

Priors are probably the most important subject within the Bayesian framework. Priors represent what we know about the important parameters of our model. For instance, a physical range where a parameter has equal probability to lie. Alternatively, the parameter's probability can be given by a distribution based on previous estimates. There are several types of priors, but in this work only two will be discussed with some detail. Priors can be broadly classified into two types: informative and uninformative.

A **uniform prior** is an uninformative prior. These are used only when we know very little about a parameter ϕ_i . For instance, that it lies inside a range $[a, b]$. Uniform priors can be used for the eccentricity of an elliptical orbit, since it ranges between 0 and 1, or the angle of periastron, that ranges between 0 and 2π . If a parameter ϕ_i lies between a and b with equal probability, its uniform prior is given by

$$\mathcal{U}(\phi_i; a, b) = \begin{cases} (b - a)^{-1} & \text{if } a \leq \phi_i \leq b \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.6)$$

A **Gaussian prior** is an informative prior. These are useful when, for a given parameter, we have a previous measurement and its $1 - \sigma$ uncertainty, and we want to use this information to weight the probability. For instance, if we have previous measurements of the orbital period of an exoplanet and we want to use this information to inform a future estimate, we can use the measurement and uncertainty of it to provide a Gaussian prior. A Gaussian prior for a given parameter ϕ_i with median a and standard deviation b is given by

$$\mathcal{N}(\phi_i; a, b) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi b^2}} \exp\left[-\frac{(\phi_i - a)^2}{2b^2}\right] \quad (3.7)$$

3.3.3 Model Evidence

In eq. (3.1) the term $P(D)$ is called model evidence but also marginal likelihood. By definition is calculated as an integral of the likelihood and prior distributions in the parameter space

$$P(D) = \int P(D|M(\vec{\phi}))P(M(\vec{\phi}))d\vec{\phi} \quad (3.8)$$

3.3.4 Marginal Posterior Distribution

All the components needed to calculate $P(M|D)$ from eq. (3.1) are already mentioned. Now, in order to derive physical parameters ϕ_i we need to focus on the posterior distribution of each parameter instead on its normalised probability. The term $P(D|M)P(M)$ called *non-normalised posterior probability distribution function* is where the physical parameters can be extracted. This is the maximum value given by the posterior distribution is taken. If we were using the normalised posterior probability, Since M is a parametric model, we can marginalise the parameters ϕ_i by integrating $P(D|M)P(M)$ over the remaining $\phi_{i \neq j}$ parameters. This leads to a marginal posterior distribution for each parameter ϕ_i from which we can infer the model parameters.

Figure 3.1 shows how priors can affect the final posterior distribution for a fixed likelihood. For instance, the upper and lower limits of a flat prior may truncate or exclude the maximum of the likelihood function. The influence of a Gaussian prior on the posterior distribution depends on the prior's center and width, as well as on the number of data points

Figure 3.1: Posterior distributions (solid red line) for a fixed likelihood (blue dashed lines) and different priors (green dot-dashed lines). All quantities have been normalized for comparison purpose. *Upper left*: Uniform prior with limits $[-3, 3]$. *Upper right*: Uniform prior with limits $[-3, 0]$. *Lower left*: Gaussian prior with mean 1.5 and standard deviation 1.5. *Lower right*: Gaussian prior with mean 1.5 and standard deviation 0.3

3.4 Markov Chain Monte Carlo

In order to obtain the marginal posterior distribution we can use several methods. Sometimes the calculations can be made analytically but most of the times numerical methods are needed. For instance, iterative methods are very useful when it comes to generate marginal posterior distributions from a collection of data points. A *Markov chain* is very useful for this purpose.

Following the definition of Sharma (2017), a Markov chain is a sequence of random variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n such that, given the present state depends only on the previous position, such that the future and past are independent. The most important aspect of a Markov chain is that the next iteration depends only on the current one. If a stochastic process is used to generate Markov chains, this method is called Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), like the famous casino. The importance of this method is that these random variables can be the points $\vec{\phi}$ in the parameter space we want to sample. We can generate a set of N models from an initial guess of $\vec{\phi}$.

There are several MCMC sampling methods. A classic MCMC algorithm is the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm (see Metropolis et al., 1953; Hastings, 1970). For this thesis, we are using a parallelised ensemble sampler algorithm (see e.g. Goodman & Weare, 2010; Foreman-Mackey et al., 2013) used in the code `pyaneti` (Barragán et al., 2019a).

3.5 Parallelised ensemble sampler algorithm

The *ensemble* sampler algorithm is in fact just a group of Markov chains used to explore the parameter space. Each chain j starts with a point in the parameters space $\vec{\phi}_{j,t}$ and evolve according to the *complementary* (remaining) chains of the ensemble. This algorithm involves an ensemble S of K simultaneously-evolving chains ($S = X_k$ where S is the ensemble). The proposal distribution for one chain k is based on the current positions of the $K - 1$ chains in the complementary ensemble ($S_{[k]} = X_j, \forall j \neq k$). It is important to state that “position” in this context means a vector in the n -dimensional and real-valued parameter space.

Details of the ensemble sampler algorithm can be found in Barragán et al. (2019a). It suffices to say that it is a method that parallelize the sampling algorithm by simultaneously advancing each chain based on the state of the ensemble instead of evolving the chains in series. This parallelization process significantly outperforms standard Metropolis-Hastings algorithm.

3.6 `pyaneti`

`pyaneti` is the code used in this thesis to perform the analysis of the systems mentioned in section 1.8. It is a software suitable to simultaneously fit RV and transit light curves of multi-planet systems. `pyaneti` combines the computational power of FORTRAN with the versatility of PYTHON and it offers the option to run in parallel with *OpenMP*. It implements a Bayesian statistics framework along with a MCMC sampling in order to explore the parameter space of the fitted parameters that we might have. One of the main advantages of `pyaneti` is that all the code controls are given inside a PYTHON-based input file. Priors, fitted parameters, and data files are controlled via flags and python objects. This allows us to run the code with only one command line. The interested reader can visit `pyaneti` github page¹, where he or she will find very detailed instructions about how to install `pyaneti` and how to use it for analysing RV and transit light curves. There are

¹See: <https://github.com/oscaribv/pyaneti>

several tutorials regarding how to use `pyaneti` to characterise well-known systems, like 51 Peg b, K2-98, the Earth or even TRAPPIST-1.

In Sections 2.1 and 2.3 it was shown how RV and Transit methods work, respectively. The measurements used in those methods correspond to the data D in terms of Bayesian analysis. That data D can be compared with the parametric model M described on the same sections (see e.g., Mandel & Agol, 2002, model for transits). With both data D and model M we can use the Bayesian analysis and MCMC sampling discussed in this chapter to explain how `pyaneti` works.

3.6.1 Parametric models

The general parametric function that describes how a planet (or planets) orbiting a star changes its radial velocity is given by

$$f_{RV}(\vec{\phi}; t) = f(\{T_0, P, e, \omega_*, K\}_\alpha, \gamma_\beta; t) \quad (3.9)$$

where the set of planetary parameters T_0, P, e, ω_*, K repeats for each planet α and γ_β for each instrument β .

The general parametric function that describes planetary transits is the following:

$$f_{tr}(\vec{\phi}; t) = f(\{T_0, P, e, \omega_*, R_p/R_*, a/R_*, i\}_\alpha, \{u_1, u_2\}_\epsilon; t) \quad (3.10)$$

where the set of parameters $\{T_0, P, e, \omega_*, R_p/R_*, a/R_*, i\}$ repeats for each planet α . Each $\{u_1, u_2\}$ repeats for each photometric band ϵ of the light curve.

It can be seen from equations (3.9) and (3.10) that there are four shared parameters between RV and Transit equations: T_0, P, e, ω_* . With `pyaneti` it is possible to fit simultaneously the orbital parameters for both RV and Tr data. In general, transit data improves the values of the ephemeris, T_0 and P , while RV data constrains e and ω_* . The parameters involved in a joint fit are:

$$\vec{\phi} = (\{T_0, P, e, \omega_*, R_p/R_*, a/R_*, i, K\}_\alpha, \gamma_\beta, \{u_1, u_2\}_\epsilon; t) \quad (3.11)$$

Where $\{T_0, P, e, \omega_*, R_p/R_*, a/R_*, i, K\}$ repeats for each planet α , $\{u_1, u_2\}$ for each band ϵ and γ for each instrument β . Equations (3.9), (3.10) and (3.11) can be used in eq. (3.4) to compare with a given dataset D composed of both RV and light curve data. The important thing about all this is that by using priors for the planetary parameters in (3.11) we can estimate a posterior distribution for each parameter using MCMC sampling methods.

3.6.2 Parametrizations of `pyaneti`

Equation (3.11) defines the general set of parameters that can be extracted by modeling RV measurements and transit photometry. It is possible to use a set of convenient parametrizations to improve the exploration of the parameter space and avoid biases due to priors. In the following sub-sections we provide a brief description of the parametrizations used by `pyaneti`.

Eccentricity and Angle of Periastron

The posterior distribution of the eccentricity is not well sampled for orbits with small eccentricities. A practical solution is to define e and ω_* using a polar representation. In `pyaneti` the parametrization of Anderson et al. (2011) is used

$$ew_1 = \sqrt{e} \sin \omega_*, \quad ew_2 = \sqrt{e} \cos \omega_* \quad (3.12)$$

This parameterization has two advantages: a) it is not truncated when the eccentricity is close to zero; b) uniform priors on ew_1 and ew_2 imply uniform priors on the eccentricity.

Impact factor

As presented in Sec 2.4, the transit of a planet can be described using the scaled projected distance between the planet and star centers. It is then convenient to parametrize the stellar inclination using a parameter that takes into account the projected distance. A practical approach is via the impact parameter defined as

$$b = \frac{a}{R_*} \cos i \left(\frac{1 - e^2}{1 + e \sin \omega_*} \right) \quad (3.13)$$

The advantage of using the impact factor is that b can be compared directly with the projected distance. In this way it is easy to set priors to exclude orbits for which there is no transit, i.e., when $b > 1 + r_p$.

Limb darkening coefficients

For the limb darkening coefficients `pyaneti` uses the parametrization proposed by Kipping (2013), who showed that an optimal way to sample the parameter space for the Mandel & Agol (2002) limb darkening coefficients is via the parametrization

$$q_1 = (u_1 + u_2)^2, \quad q_2 = \frac{u_1}{2(u_1 + u_2)} \quad (3.14)$$

The advantage of this approach is that it fully accounts for our ignorance about the intensity profile and explores physical solutions by sampling uniformly q_1 and q_2 between 0 and 1.

Stellar density

Equation (2.17) relates stellar density and orbital parameters like P and a/R_* that can be used to compare stellar density derived from the modelling of the transit light curves with an independent determination (e.g., from spectroscopy).

It is convenient to parametrize a/R_* with ρ_* . If precise stellar parameters have been calculated, it is possible to set tight priors on the stellar density and hence on a/R_* . For a multi-planet system, it is convenient to parameterize the scaled semi-major axis a_j/R_* of all planets j using the same stellar density. In this way the stellar density is constrained for all planets and Kepler's third law is not violated within planets orbiting the same star.

Chapter 4

Characterisation of Exoplanets

There was someone with eyes
closed on the upper floors

Charles Simic, The white room.

In this chapter we present the planetary systems that have been characterised in the course of this thesis project. They are:

- **K2-106 b and c**: Two systems already studied by [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#).
- **K2-141 b and c**: An USP planet studied by [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and a grazing transiting planet (K2-141 c) reported by [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#).
- **HD-3167 b, and c**: Two systems already studied by [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#)

For the characterisation of the exoplanets of this thesis we performed different analyses with the scientific code `pyaneti`. This analysis was divided in two stages: In the first stage we performed a transit fit. In order to perform it, we took into account the information of the respective authors of each system and we created our priors according to that information. Then, in the second stage, we performed a RV fit. For this fit we used as Gaussian priors the ephemeris obtained with the transit fit of the first stage. In the following section we present the two methods that we used for the RV fit of our analysis and later we present the transit models and *K2* photometry that we used.

4.1 Methods for measuring the Doppler semi-amplitude

4.1.1 Floating Chunk offset (FCO) method

In this section we present the two methods used in our RV analyses. The first one is the so-called Floating Chunk Offset (FCO) method, first used by [Hatzes et al. \(2011\)](#). This method is an excellent tool in the RV analysis of USP planets. The reason for this is that with the FCO method we are able to get rid of the RV signals associated with longer periods, conserving only signals associated with shorter periods.

This method divides a given RV dataset in several portions (chunks) of duration Δt . These portions have to be small but big enough in order to encompass a significant part of an orbital planetary

signal. If there are RV signals with periods $\gg \Delta t$, these signals can be interpreted as constant in every time chunk, Δt . Therefore, we can get rid of those signals. For each chunk we can fit an offset that accounts for the longer period signals in order to get rid of them.

The FCO method is excellent when it comes to analysing USP planets. For instance, if the signal of an USP planet is inside a given RV dataset, we can cover a significant fraction of that signal by taking multiple RV measurements per night. Then we can divide the RV dataset in nightly chunks and fit for an offset for each night.

In this thesis, we used the FCO method for the three USP planets of the systems: [K2-106 b](#), [K2-141 b](#) and [HD 3167 b](#). It is remarkable to say that the FCO method can be performed by `pyaneti` once a RV dataset is divided in chunks.

4.1.2 Pre-whitening

The second method used in our RV analysis is the Pre-whitening. This method is based in using Keplerian signals to model RV measurements. This method is very useful; specially when it comes to analyse RV datasets contaminated with stellar activity. RV variations due to active regions (solar-like spots) coupled to stellar rotational modulation can be complex with not only the stellar rotational period of the star, but also its harmonics (e.g. $P/2$, $P/3$, ...). If we assume that active regions are not evolving fast, then the simplest representation of the rotational modulation is through Fourier components defined by the rotation period and their harmonics.

If the time scale of the rotation period of the star and their active regions larger than the one of RV measurements, we can assume that any activity-induced RV signal is coherent inside the observing time scale. Therefore we can model those activity-induced RV signals with Keplerian signals. This approach has been used by several authors (e.g. [Barragán et al., 2018a](#); [Pepe et al., 2013](#)) for detecting planetary signals in RV measurements of active stars. This method for dealing with activity-induced RV signals is used in this thesis for the analysis of K2-141 and HD 3167 with `pyaneti`.

4.2 K2 Photometry and detrending.

For the transit analysis of this thesis we used the *K2* photometry datasets provided by [Vanderburg & Johnson \(2014\)](#)¹ for K2-106, K2-141 and HD 3167.

1. K2-106 was observed by the space mission during campaign 8 (C8), carried out from January 03, 2016, to March 23, 2016, UTC.
2. K2-141 was observed by *K2*'s campaign 12 (C12), carried out from December 15, 2016, to March 4, 2017, UTC and by campaign 19 (C19), carried out from August 29, 2018, to September 26, 2018, UTC.
3. HD 3167 was observed also during campaign 8 (C8).

We note that the light curves provided by [Vanderburg & Johnson \(2014\)](#) are not flat. They contain flux modulations caused by intrinsic stellar signals (e.g., modulation caused by spot on the

¹*K2* campaigns from 0 to 19 and can be found in [here](#), the page of *K2* Photometry by Andrew Vanderburg.

stellar surface) together with instrumental systematics (e.g., telescope motion). Therefore, before modelling the transits, we proceed to remove such trends. This process is usually called *detrending*.

We detrended the *K2* light curves using the public code [citlalicue](#)². Briefly, `citlalicue` uses Gaussian Processes (GPs)³ as implemented in `george` (Ambikasaran et al., 2015) to model the intrinsic variability in the out-of-transit data, together with `pytransit` (Parviainen, 2015) to predict the times at which transits occur. We mask out all the transits when fitting the GP, and remove outliers by clipping at ± 5 -sigma. We then divide by the GP model to obtain a detrended light curve containing transits only. We detrended each *K2* campaign independently. Figures 4.1a, 4.1b, 4.1c, and 4.1d show the un-detrended and detrended light curves for K2-106, K2-141, and HD 3167, respectively. We then use the flattened version of the light curves to perform all the transit analysis described in the remainder of this chapter.

²See: <https://pypi.org/project/citlalicue/>

³We note that Gaussian Processes are a generalisation of the multi-variate Gaussian distribution to the continuous space that allows to generate data-driven non-parametric functions. A detailed description of GPs is out of the scope of this thesis. The interested reader can revise specialised literature (e.g., Roberts et al., 2013).

(a) *K2*'s light curve of K2-106 detrended with *citlalicue*.

(b) *K2*'s Campaign 12 light curve of K2-141 detrended with *citlalicue*.

(c) *K2*'s Campaign 19 light curve of K2-141 detrended with *citlalicue*.

(d) *K2*'s light curve of HD 3167 detrended with *citlalicue*.

Figure 4.1: Normalised *K2* light curve for K2-106 (panel a), K2-141 (panel b) and HD 3167 (panel c). In each panel, the raw light curve is indicated by gray dots, while the numerous transits of the USP planets are represented as the blue inverted triangles. The scarce transits of the outer planets can be seen as the orange inverted triangles. On the bottom of the figure it can be seen the flattened light curve.

4.3 K2-106

The discovery of two transiting exoplanets around the star K2-106 was first reported by [Adams et al. \(2017\)](#). They used photometric data from *K2*'s campaign number 8. Then, several and intensive RV follow-up observations were presented in [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#). The physical estimation of K2-106 b and K2-106 c will be presented in this section. This estimation was performed using *K2*'s light curve data as well as the RV datasets of both [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#).

4.3.1 Transit analysis

In the transit analysis of K2-106 we performed a 2-planet fit with `pyaneti`. In the fit we used [Mandel & Agol \(2002\)](#) model and [Kipping \(2013\)](#) parametrisation of limb darkening coefficients. We fitted for the stellar density of the host star and we assumed a circular orbit for the two transiting exoplanets. We used flat uniform priors for every parameter of the fit. Those priors were created taking into account the results reported by [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#). Details about the priors for the transit fit of K2-106 can be seen in Table 4.1. In order to generate a posterior distribution of 250 000 independent points for each parameter, we explored the parameter space with 500 Markov chains, 500 iterations and a thin factor equal to 10. A thin factor greater than 1 is useful for decreasing the auto-correlation of the simulated MCMC sample and it gives a better estimation of the posterior distribution. This is because auto-correlation produce *clumpy* samples that are unrepresentative, in the short run, of the true underlying posterior distribution. Since *K2* space mission used long-cadence data during campaign 8, i.e., every 29.4 minutes took lectures, we did integrate our transit data every 29.4 min with 30 steps of integration ([Kipping, 2010](#)). The inferred value of each parameter and its uncertainty is given by the median and 68.3% confident interval of the posterior distribution. We also did account for an additional jitter term and we obtained $\chi^2/d.o.f = 1.0082$, where *d.o.f* stands for *degrees of freedom*. Figure 4.2 shows the transit data and inferred models for K2-106 b and K2-106 c. Details about the posterior distribution can be found in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.2: Phase-folded transit light curves of K2-106 due to planet b (left panel) and c (right panel). The best fitting transit models are over-plotted with thick black lines. The *K2* data-points are shown with green circles.

Parameter	Prior ⁴	Final Value
Model parameters for the transit analysis of K2-106		
<i>Planet K2-106 b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{U}[0.570, 0.572]$	$0.571294^{+1.5e-05}_{-1.5e-05}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{U}[7394, 7394.016]$	$7394.0112^{+0.0011}_{-0.0011}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
Impact parameter, b	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.26^{+0.26}_{-0.18}$
Scaled planetary radius, r_p/R_*	$\mathcal{U}[0, 0.1]$	$0.0162^{+0.00051}_{-0.00046}$
<i>Planet K2-106 c</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{U}[13.30, 13.35]$	$13.33968^{+0.00095}_{-0.00106}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{U}[7405.72, 7405.75]$	$7405.7323^{+0.0027}_{-0.0024}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
Impact parameter, b	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.593^{+0.093}_{-0.058}$
Scaled planetary radius, r_p/R_*	$\mathcal{U}[0, 0.1]$	$0.02731^{+0.0008}_{-0.00071}$
<i>Other parameters</i>		
Stellar density [g/cm^3]	$\mathcal{U}[0.01, 5]$	$1.34^{+0.2}_{-0.35}$
Limb darkening q_1	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.4^{+0.35}_{-0.23}$
Limb darkening q_2	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.3^{+0.33}_{-0.2}$

Table 4.1: K2-106 system parameters for the transit analysis.

⁴ $\mathcal{U}[a, b]$ means uniform priors between a and b , $\mathcal{N}[a, b]$ means Gaussian priors with mean a and standard deviation b and $\mathcal{F}[a]$ means a prior fixed to a value a .

Figure 4.3: Posterior distributions functions for the derived parameters of the transit fit of K2-106 with `pyaneti`. The green region corresponds to the posterior $P(M|D)$, the blue line corresponds to the prior $P(M)$, the 68% confident interval is shown in red, the mode is the yellow dashed line and the mean is the black line. The value we adopted is the mean and the uncertainty corresponds to $1 - \sigma$.

4.3.2 RV analyses: FCO and Pre-whitening

We first performed a FCO method model of the RV data of K2-106 . We selected the HARPS-N, HARPS and KECK measurements for which at least two data points were taken the same night. This leads to a number of 3, 8 and 5 chunks of nightly data from HARPS-N, HARPS and KECK respectively. With this chunk division we were able to use `pyaneti` to perform the FCO method for K2-106 b.

We set Gaussian priors on the time of mid-transit and period based on our analysis given in Section 4.3.1. For the remaining parameters we used uniform priors created according to the information of [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#). We used 700 Markov chains, 500 iterations and a thin factor of 100 in order to generate a posterior distribution of 350 000 independent points for each parameter. We used 700 Markov chains because the chunks of K2-106 b increased the dimension of our parameter space such that we needed to use a huge number of Markov chains to sample the parameters. We also did account for a jitter term for every spectrograph in the fit and we obtained a $\chi^2/d.o.f = 1.2967$. In Figure 4.4 it is shown the phase-folded FCO curve for K2-106 b. We found a radial velocity semi-amplitude variation of $K = 6.20^{+1.13}_{-1.21} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for K2-106 b.

Figure 4.4: Phase-folded RV curve of K2-106 b folded to the orbital period of the planet, as obtained using FCO method. The best fitting solution is marked with a solid black line. RV data chunks from HARPS-N, HARPS and KECK are shown with different colors.

We then reanalysed the RV data using a Pre-whitening with `pyaneti`. This allowed us to model the signals for both planets in the system. We used only two Keplerian signals for this RV fit. Any additional signal was not necessary since K2-106 is a relatively quiet star. We set Gaussian priors for the time of mid-transit and period based on the values obtained by the transit fit. For the remaining parameters we used uniform priors created according to the information of [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#). We explored the parameter space with 500 Markov chains,

500 iterations and a thin factor of 10 in order to generate a posterior distribution of 250 000 independent points for each parameter of each planet. We also did account for a jitter term for every spectrograph we used and we obtained a $\chi^2/d.o.f = 1.1675$. Figure 4.5 shows the RV time-series with the data of all instruments, as well as the phase-folded RV signals for K2-106 b and K2-106 c. Details about the posterior distribution for the RV fit via FCO and Pre-whitening are shown in Figure 4.6. We show the results for both analyses in Table 4.2. We note that the Doppler semi-amplitude for planet K2-106 b is consistent within one sigma between two methods, FCO and Pre-whitening. This gives confidence to our estimate. We found for K2-106 b a Doppler-semi amplitude of $6.63^{+0.68}_{-0.67} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ with Pre-whitening.

Figure 4.5: On the top panel the RV time-series of K2-106 is shown. The data points of HARPS-N, HARPS, PFS, HDS, FIES and KECK are represented with different colors and symbols. On the bottom left the phase-folded RV curve of K2-106 b is shown. On the bottom right the phase-folded RV curve of K2-106 c is shown.

Parameter	Prior ⁵	Final Value
Model parameters for FCO method		
<i>Planet K2-106 b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[0.571293, 0.000015]$	$0.571285^{+1.4e-05}_{-1.4e-05}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7394.0111, 0.0011]$	$7394.0111^{+0.0011}_{-0.0011}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$6.22^{+1.13}_{-1.21}$
Model parameters for Pre-whitening		
<i>Planet K2-106 b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[0.571293, 0.000015]$	$0.571294^{+1.2e-05}_{-1.2e-05}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7394.01119, 0.0011]$	$7394.0112^{+0.0011}_{-0.0011}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$6.63^{+0.69}_{-0.68}$
<i>Planet K2-106 c</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[13.3396, 0.00105]$	$13.3397^{+0.001}_{-0.001}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7405.7323, 0.00273]$	$7405.7323^{+0.0028}_{-0.0027}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$1.47^{+0.78}_{-0.74}$

Table 4.2: K2-106 system parameters for the RV analyses.

⁵ $\mathcal{U}[a, b]$ means uniform priors between a and b , $\mathcal{N}[a, b]$ means Gaussian priors with mean a and standard deviation b and $\mathcal{F}[a]$ means a prior fixed to a value a .

Figure 4.6: Posterior distributions of the K2-106’s RV fitted parameters as obtained from the final analysis with `pyaneti`. The green region corresponds to the posterior $P(M|D)$, whereas the blue line marks the prior shape $P(M)$. Mean (black solid line), 68% confident interval (red solid region) and mode (yellow dashed line) are also shown.

4.4 K2-141

K2-141 was confirmed as a planetary system independently by [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#). They used photometric data from *K2*'s campaign 12. Then, several and intensive RV follow-up observations were presented by both teams. The parameter estimation of K2-141 b and K2-141 c will be presented in this section. This estimation was performed using *K2*'s light curve data from campaigns 12 and 19 as well the RV datasets from both [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#).

4.4.1 Transit analysis

In the transit analysis of K2-141 we performed a 2-planet fit with `pyaneti` as for K2-106. We used [Mandel & Agol \(2002\)](#) model and [Kipping \(2013\)](#) parametrisation of limb darkening coefficients. Since we are dealing with two different observation campaigns, we performed a *multi-band* fit for K2-141. We used two different bands, one for each campaign. The reason for this is the following: Although all *K2*'s campaigns were performed at the same wavelength, some used long-cadence data and others short-cadence. This creates a difference when creating the model to compute the likelihood. We re-sampled the model over 10 steps to account for the long-cadence (30min) data of campaign 12 ([Kipping, 2010](#)) but we did not re-sample the model for the short-cadence of campaign 19. We assumed that the difference of transit depth between different bands is negligible; therefore, we fitted for a single radius ratio R_p/R_* for all the bands. We also fitted for the stellar density of the host star and we assumed a circular orbit for both planets. This multi-band procedure has been used for other systems as well (see e.g. [Barragán et al., 2019b](#), for a multi-band transit analysis of K2-100b). We used flat uniform priors for every parameter of our transit fit. Those priors were created taking into account the results reported by [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#). We note that K2-141 c transits are grazing, i.e., the full disc of the planet never falls completely in the stellar disc at any time of the transit ([Malavolta et al., 2018](#)). This generates a continuous transition between ingress and egress that creates a V-shaped transit light curve. Therefore, the radius of the planet cannot be determined, only a minimum radius (see e.g., [Grziwa et al., 2016](#)). When modelling grazing transits there is a degeneracy due to a coupling between the scaled-planet radius and impact parameter. In order to truncate this degeneracy, we assumed that K2-141 c is not bigger than 10% the radius of the star, and we set a prior for the impact parameter between 0 and 1.1, and for the scaled radius of 0.1. Further details about priors for the transit fit of K2-141 can be seen in Table 4.3. We explored the parameter space with 500 Markov chains, 500 iterations and a thin factor equal to 10 in order to generate a posterior distribution of 250 000 independent points for each parameter. The inferred value of each parameter and its uncertainty is given by the median and 68.3% confident interval of the posterior distribution. We also did account for an additional jitter term and we obtained $\chi^2/d.of. = 1.0002$. Figure 4.7 shows the transit data and inferred models for K2-141 b and K2-141 c. Details about the posterior distributions can be found in Figure 4.9 .

K2's campaign 19 was the last one of *K2*. By that time, the data were highly-impacted by instrumental error and the satellite was running out of fuel. This is why observation campaign 19 only lasted 10 days. And since K2-141 c has an orbital period of ~ 7.7 days, *K2* was lucky enough to observe it transiting once (See Figure 4.1c). The importance in using two observation campaigns for a transit fit lies on the fact that the error in the ephemeris (T_0 and P) propagates through time. By using two different observation campaigns we can improve these values and reduce the

uncertainties of the radii estimation. Figure 4.8 compares our ephemeris from our 2-campaign transit fit (green region) with the ones obtained by Barragán et al. (2018b) from their 1-campaign transit fit (blue region).

Figure 4.7: *K2*'s data points and transit light curves of K2-141 b (left) and K2-141 c (right). The best fitting transit models are over plotted with thick black lines. *K2*'s datapoints are shown with green circles (C12) and red circles (C19).

Figure 4.8: The error on the ephemeris propagates throughout the passage of time. Time in years is on the x-axis. The midpoint error, in minutes of time, is on the y-axis. The blue shaded region shows the error propagation of the ephemeris obtained by Barragán et al. (2018b) using only *K2*'s campaign 12. The error propagation obtained by Malavolta et al. (2018) should be homologous. The green shaded region shows the error propagation of the ephemeris using both campaign 12 and 19. The green shaded region corresponds to the analysis of this thesis.

Parameter	Prior ⁶	Final Value
Model parameters for the transit analysis of K2-141		
<i>Planet K2-141 b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{U}[0.28032, 0.28034]$	$0.28032477^{+1.2e-07}_{-1.2e-07}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{U}[7738.4643, 7738.4666]$	$7738.46497^{+0.0002}_{-0.00019}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
Impact parameter, b	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.34^{+0.19}_{-0.22}$
Scaled planetary radius, r_p/R_*	$\mathcal{U}[0, 0.1]$	$0.02096^{+0.00032}_{-0.00028}$
<i>Planet K2-141 c</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{U}[7.748, 7.750]$	$7.74887^{+0.0003}_{-0.00028}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{U}[7751.1270, 7751.1562]$	$7751.1517^{+0.0015}_{-0.0014}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
Impact parameter, b	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1.1]$	$1.02^{+0.03}_{-0.026}$
Scaled planetary radius, r_p/R_*	$\mathcal{U}[0, 0.1]$	$0.057^{+0.026}_{-0.02}$
<i>Other parameters</i>		
Stellar density [g/cm^{-3}]	$\mathcal{U}[0.01, 5]$	$2.77^{+0.22}_{-0.22}$
Limb darkening q_1 (C12)	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.309^{+0.137}_{-0.08}$
Limb darkening q_2 (C12)	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.77^{+0.15}_{-0.22}$
Limb darkening q_1 (C19)	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.73^{+0.19}_{-0.25}$
Limb darkening q_2 (C19)	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.12^{+0.137}_{-0.08}$

Table 4.3: K2-141 system parameters for transit analysis.

⁶ $\mathcal{U}[a, b]$ means uniform priors between a and b , $\mathcal{N}[a, b]$ means Gaussian priors with mean a and standard deviation b and $\mathcal{F}[a]$ means a prior fixed to a value a .

Figure 4.9: Posterior distributions of the K2-141’s transit fitted parameters as obtained from `pyaneti`. The green region corresponds to the posterior $P(M|D)$, whereas the blue line marks the prior shape $P(M)$. Mean (black solid line), 68% confident interval (red solid region) and mode (yellow dashed line) are also shown.

4.4.2 RV analyses: FCO and Pre-whitening

We first performed a FCO method model of the RV dataset of K2-141. We selected the HARPS-N, HARPS and FIES measurements for which at least two data points were taken the same night. This leads to 14, 7 and 3 chunks of nightly data from HARPS-N, HARPS and FIES, respectively. With this chunk division of the RV dataset we were able to use `pyaneti` to perform the FCO method for K2-141 b.

We set Gaussian priors of mid-transit and period based on the transit analysis of section 4.4.1. For the remaining parameters we used uniform priors created according to the information given by [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#). We used 700 Markov chains, 500 iterations and a thin factor of 100 in order to generate a posterior distribution of 350 000 independent points for each parameter. We also applied a jitter term for every spectrograph that we used and we obtained a $\chi^2/d.o.f = 1.1965$. Figure 4.10 shows the RV data together with the inferred model once all the night offsets were subtracted. We found a radial velocity semi-amplitude variation of $K = 6.38^{+0.39}_{-0.38} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for K2-141 b with the FCO method.

Figure 4.10: The RV curve of K2-141 phase-folded to the orbital period of planet b, as derived using FCO method. The best fitting circular solution is marked with a black line. Different colours represent measurements from different nights.

We then reanalysed the RV data performing a Pre-whitening with `pyaneti`. This allowed us to model the RV signals of both K2-141 b and K2-141 c. Since K2-141 is an active star, both [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#) RV datasets were affected by an activity-induced RV signal. In order to account for this signal, we followed the procedure detailed in [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#). The procedure consists in adding an extra sinusoidal signal to our RV analysis, as [Pepe et al. \(2013\)](#) did. The period of this extra sinusoidal signal was constrained with a Gaussian prior. This prior is centered at the rotational period of the star, $P_{rot} = 14.03 \pm 0.09$ days, that is known since [McQuillan et al. \(2014\)](#). In Figure 4.8 the RV signal associated with stellar activity is shown.

This extra sinusoidal signal is added as we would add a –non-transiting– planet in the RV analysis we performed in `pyaneti`. We are tricking `pyaneti` in terms of performing a 3-planet fit instead of a 2-planet fit. While a 2-planet fit for K2-141 results in a $\chi^2/d.o.f \sim 5$, a 3-planet fit gives a $\chi^2/d.o.f = 1.1003$. This shows clearly that the activity-induced RV signal has to be taken into account. We set Gaussian priors for the time of mid-transit and period based on the values obtained by the transit fit. For the remaining parameters we used uniform priors created according to [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#). We explored the parameter space with 500 Markov chains, 500 iterations and a thin factor of 10 in order to generate a posterior distribution of 250 000 independent points for each parameter of each planet. We also account for a jitter term for every spectrograph in our fit. Figure 4.12 shows the RV time-series with the data of all instruments, as well as the phase-folded RV signals due to K2-141 b and K2-141 c. Details about the posterior distributions for the RV fit via FCO and Pre-whitening are shown in Figure 4.13. We show the results for both analyses in Table 4.4. We note that the Doppler semi-amplitude for K2-141 b is consistent within one sigma between Pre-whitening and FCO method. We obtained a Doppler semi-amplitude of $6.67^{+0.56}_{-0.56} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for K2-141 b with Pre-whitening.

Figure 4.11: Phase-folded RV curve of the activity induced signal with a period centred at 14.03 days.

Figure 4.12: On the top panel the RV time-series of K2-141 is shown. The data points of FIES, HARPS and HARPS-N, are represented with different colors and symbols. On the bottom left the phase-folded RV curve of K2-141 b. On the bottom right the phase-folded RV curve of K2-141 c.

Parameter	Prior	Final Value
Model parameters for FCO method		
<i>Planet K2-141 b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[0.2803248, 0.0000001]$	$0.2803242^{+1.4e-06}_{-1.4e-06}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7738.4650, 0.0002]$	$77738.3949^{+0.0002}_{-0.0002}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$6.38^{+0.39}_{-0.39}$
Model parameters for Pre-whitening		
<i>Planet K2-141 b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[0.2803248, 0.0000001]$	$0.280324799^{+1e-07}_{-9.9e-08}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7738.4650, 0.0002]$	$77738.4649^{+0.0002}_{-0.0002}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$6.67^{+0.56}_{-0.56}$
<i>Planet K2-141 c</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[7.74887, 0.0003]$	$7.74887^{+0.00029}_{-0.0003}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7751.1517, 0.0015]$	$77751.1517^{+0.0015}_{-0.0015}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$2.39^{+0.99}_{-0.97}$
<i>Activity Signal $P = 14.03$ days</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb}	$\mathcal{N}[14.03, 0.09]$	$14.012^{+0.088}_{-0.089}$
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$5.12^{+0.61}_{-0.56}$

Table 4.4: K2-141 system parameters for RV analyses.

Figure 4.13: Posterior distributions of the K2-141's RV fitted parameters as obtained from the final analysis with `pyaneti`. The green region corresponds to the posterior $P(M|D)$, whereas the blue line marks the prior shape $P(M)$. Mean (black solid line), 68% confident interval (red solid region) and mode (yellow dashed line) are also shown.

4.5 HD 3167

The validation of HD 3167 as a planetary system was first reported by [Vanderburg et al. \(2016\)](#). They used photometric data from *K2*'s campaign 8. Then, several and intensive RV follow-up observations were presented by [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#). The parameter estimation of HD 3167 b and HD 3167 c is presented in this section. This estimation was performed using *K2*'s light curve data as well as the RV datasets of both [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#).

4.5.1 Transit analysis

In the transit analysis of HD 3167 we performed a 2-planet fit with `pyaneti`. We used the procedure described in section 4.4.1. We fitted for the stellar density of the host star and we assumed a circular orbit for the two transiting exoplanets. We used flat uniform priors for every parameter of the fit. Those priors were created taking into account the results reported by [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#). Details about the priors for the transit fit of HD 3167 can be seen in Table 4.5. We explored the parameter space with 500 Markov chains, 500 iterations and a thin factor equal to 10 in order to generate a posterior distribution of 250 000 independent points for each parameter. Since *K2* space mission used long-cadence data, we did integrate our transit data every 29.4 minutes, with 30 steps of integration. We also applied a jitter term and we obtained $\chi^2/d.o.f = 1.0005$. Figure 4.14 shows the transit data and inferred models for HD 3167 b and HD 3167 c. Details about the posterior distributions can be found in Figure 4.15.

Figure 4.14: *K2*'s data points and transit light curves of HD 3167 b (left) and HD 3167 c (right). The best fitting transit models are overlapped with thick black lines. *K2*'s datapoints are shown with green circles.

Parameter	Prior	Final Value
Model parameters for the transit analysis of HD 3167		
<i>Planet HD 3167 b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{U}[0.570, 0.572]$	$0.571^{+0.00001}_{-0.00001}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{U}[7394, 7394.016]$	$7394.0112^{+0.0011}_{-0.0010}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
Impact parameter, b	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.256^{+0.257}_{-0.178}$
Scaled planetary radius, r_p/R_*	$\mathcal{U}[0, 0.1]$	$0.0162^{+0.0005}_{-0.0004}$
<i>Planet HD 3167 c</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{U}[13.30, 13.35]$	$13.339^{+0.001}_{-0.001}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{U}[7405.72, 7405.75]$	$7405.7323^{+0.0027}_{-0.0023}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
Impact parameter, b	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.593^{+0.092}_{-0.058}$
Scaled planetary radius, r_p/R_*	$\mathcal{U}[0, 0.1]$	$0.0273^{+0.0008}_{-0.0007}$
<i>Other parameters</i>		
Stellar density [g/cm^3]	$\mathcal{U}[0.01, 5]$	$1.341^{+0.203}_{-0.348}$
Limb darkening q_1	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.401^{+0.348}_{-0.231}$
Limb darkening q_2	$\mathcal{U}[0, 1]$	$0.298^{+0.325}_{-0.203}$

Table 4.5: HD 3167 system parameters for the transit analysis.

Figure 4.15: Posterior distributions for the derived parameters of the transit fit of HD 3167 with `pyaneti`. The green region corresponds to the posterior $P(M|D)$, whereas the blue line does mark the prior shape $P(M)$. Mean (black solid line), 68% confident interval (red solid region) and mode (yellow dashed line) are also shown.

4.5.2 RV analyses: FCO and Pre-whitening

We first used the FCO method to model the RV data of HD 3167 b. We selected the FIES, HARPS, HARPS-N, APF and HIRES measurements for which at least two data points were taken the same night. This led to a number of 12, 15, 38, 31 and 22 of chunks nightly data from FIES, HARPS, HARPS-N, APF and HIRES respectively. With this chunk division we were able to use `pyaneti` to perform a FCO method.

We set Gaussian priors on the time of mid-transit and period on our analysis given in section 4.5.1. For the remaining parameters we used uniform priors created according to the information of [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#). We used 700 Markov chains, 500 iterations and a thin factor of 100 in order to generate a posterior distribution of 350 000 independent points for each parameter. We also applied a jitter term for every spectrograph in the fit and we obtained a $\chi^2/d.o.f = 0.9844$. Figure 4.16 shows the RV data together with the inferred model once all the night offsets were subtracted. We found a radial velocity semi-amplitude variation of $K = 3.49^{+0.30}_{-0.31} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for HD 3167 b.

Figure 4.16: In this Figure the RV curve of HD 3167 phase-folded to the orbital period of planet b, as derived using the FCO method, is shown. The best fitting circular solution is marked with a black line. Different colors represent measurements from different nights.

We then reanalyse the RV data using a Pre-whitening with `pyaneti`. This allowed us to model the RV signals of HD 3167 b, HD 3167 c and HD 3167 d. Since HD 3167 is an active star, both [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#) RV datasets were affected by several activity-induced RV signals. In order to account for these signals, we followed the procedure used in our previous analysis of K2-141, in Section 4.4.2. This procedure consists in adding an extra sinusoidal signal for every activity-induced signal in our RV data. Since [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#) reported two signals associated with stellar activity, we added two sinusoidal signals to our RV fit. These two extra signals were added as we would add two –non-transiting– planets in the RV analysis

we performed with `pyaneti`. One of the signals has a period of $10.63^{+0.18}_{-0.14}$ days. The other has a period of $5.99^{+0.033}_{-0.034}$ days. The period of these signals were constrained with Gaussian priors centred at the values mentioned by [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#). This shows how we tricked `pyaneti` in terms of performing a 5-planet fit. This 5-planet fit stands for HD 3167 b and HD 3167 c, reported by both [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#), HD 3167 d, reported by [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) and then the two RV activity-induced signals reported by [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#). We set Gaussian priors for the time of mid-transit and period obtained with the transit fit. For the remaining parameters we used uniform priors created according to [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Gandolfi et al. \(2017\)](#). We explored the parameter space with 500 Markov chains, 500 iterations and a thin factor 10 in order to generate a posterior distribution of 250 000 independent points for each parameter of each planet. We also applied a jitter term for every spectrograph in our fit. Figure 4.17 shows RV time-series with the data of all instruments, as well as the phase-folded RV signals due to HD 3167 b and HD 3167 c. In figures 4.18, 4.19 and 4.20 the RV plots of the signals associated with stellar activity are shown. Posterior distributions for each fitted parameter of our RV analysis via FCO and Pre-whitening can be seen in Figure 4.21. We show the results of both analyses in Table 4.6. We note that the Doppler semi-amplitude for HD 3167 b is consistent within one sigma between Pre-whitening and FCO method. We obtained a Doppler semi-amplitude of $3.52^{+0.29}_{-0.30}$ for HD 3167 b with Pre-whitening.

Figure 4.17: On the top panel the RV time-series of HD 3167 is shown. The data points of FIES, HARPS, HARPS-N, APF and HIRES are represented with different colors and symbols. On the bottom left the phase-folded RV curve of HD 3167 b is shown. On the bottom right the phase-folded RV curve of HD 3167 c is shown.

Figure 4.18: RV phase-folded plot of HD 3167 d.

Figure 4.19: RV phase-folded plot of the RV signal induced by stellar activity of HD 3167. This signal has a period of 10.63 days.

Figure 4.20: RV phase-folded plot of the RV signal induced by stellar activity of HD 3167. This signal has a period of 5.99 days.

Parameter	Prior	Final Value
Model parameters for FCO method		
<i>Planet HD 3167b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[0.959644, 0.000019]$	$0.959637^{+1.2e-05}_{-1.2e-05}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7394.37448, 0.00089]$	$7394.37451^{+0.00043}_{-0.00043}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$3.5^{+0.31}_{-0.31}$
Model parameters for Pre-whitening		
<i>Planet HD 3167b</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[0.959644, 0.000019]$	$0.959673^{+1.8e-05}_{-1.8e-05}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7394.37448, 0.00089]$	$7394.37472^{+0.0009}_{-0.00091}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$3.52^{+0.29}_{-0.3}$
<i>Planet HD 3167 c</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[29.8468, 0.00146]$	$29.8468^{+0.0014}_{-0.0015}$
Transit epoch T_0 [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7394.9781, 0.00146]$	$7394.9782^{+0.0015}_{-0.0015}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$3.5^{+0.29}_{-0.28}$
<i>Planet HD 3167 d</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[8.4925, 0.0239]$	$8.492^{+0.017}_{-0.017}$
Time of minimal conjunction T_j [$BJD_{TDB} - 2450000$]	$\mathcal{N}[7805.97, 0.509]$	$7806.17^{+0.35}_{-0.35}$
$\sqrt{e} \sin \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
$\sqrt{e} \cos \omega$	$\mathcal{F}[0]$	0
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$1.6^{+0.29}_{-0.29}$
<i>Activity signal $P = 10.63$ days</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[10.77, 0.15]$	$10.63^{+0.18}_{-0.14}$
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$0.54^{+0.33}_{-0.34}$
<i>Activity signal 5.99 days</i>		
Orbital Period P_{orb} [days]	$\mathcal{N}[5.98, 0.04]$	$5.99^{+0.033}_{-0.034}$
RV Semi-amplitude K [m/s]	$\mathcal{U}[0, 10]$	$0.71^{+0.26}_{-0.27}$

Table 4.6: HD 3167 system parameters for RV analyses.

Figure 4.21: Posterior distributions for the derived parameters of the RV fit of HD 3167 with `pyaneti`. The green region corresponds to the posterior $P(M|D)$, whereas the blue line does mark the prior shape $P(M)$. Mean (black solid line), 68% confident interval (red solid region) and mode (yellow dashed line) are also shown. In this Figure some of the posterior distributions did not follow their respective prior shapes. This means that although we were certain about prior range where posteriors should be, our analysis showed that some posterior distributions were somewhat outside the respective prior range. This shows the power of Bayesian analysis.

Chapter 5

Discussion

Stunned by the world, I reached
an age when I threw punches at
air and cried to myself

Cesare Pavese, Ancestors.

In this chapter we present the main results of the analysis described in the previous chapter. First, we report the main results of each system of this project. Then, we give a general discussion about all the planets that were characterised during this work. Finally, we present two mass-radius diagrams, each one with a color code related to a different planetary parameter.

5.1 Planetary Parameters of K2-106

If we combine the results of Table 4.1 and 4.2 together with the stellar parameters given in [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#) (the ones used by [Dai et al., 2019](#), as well) we are able to estimate the planets' physical parameters. The planetary masses are $8.04_{-0.87}^{+0.90} M_{\oplus}$ for K2-106 b and $5.13_{-2.57}^{+2.70} M_{\oplus}$ for K2-106 c. The radius of K2-106 b is $1.73_{-0.05}^{+0.06} R_{\oplus}$ and for K2-106 c is $2.91_{-0.09}^{+0.10} R_{\oplus}$. We note that our derived planetary masses and radii are not only consistent with the ones from [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#) but also the uncertainties are lower.

Our transit analysis also gave us insights about the stellar parameters. [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) measured the stellar parameters of K2-106 carrying out their own spectral analysis with data from HARPS and HARPS-N using the the PARSEC model isochrones along with the online interface for Bayesian estimation of the stellar parameters from [da Silva et al. \(2006\)](#). They obtained $M_* = 0.945 \pm 0.063 M_{\odot}$ and $R_* = 0.869 \pm 0.088 R_{\odot}$, that gives a stellar mean density of $2.03_{-0.78}^{+0.52} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. On the other hand, [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#) used iodine-free HIRES spectra along with `isochrones` python package described by [Morton \(2015\)](#) and obtained $M_* = 0.92 \pm 0.03 M_{\odot}$ and $R_* = 0.95 \pm 0.05 R_{\odot}$, that gives a stellar mean density of $1.51_{-0.21}^{+0.27} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. In our fit of the transit we used stellar density as a free parameter and we obtained a value of $1.34_{-0.35}^{+0.20} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. This was done in order to compare the stellar density derived from the modelling of transit light curves with the one derived by spectroscopy. We note that the stellar parameters derived by [Guenther et al. \(2017\)](#) provide a systematic higher value for the stellar density than the value coming from the transit analysis. While the stellar parameters derived by [Sinukoff et al. \(2017\)](#) based on transits are fully consistent with our analysis, which is why we adopted these values in this work. This reveal that transit light curves are useful tools when it comes to constrain stellar

parameters of the host star for a given spectroscopic survey, as mentioned in Section 2.5.

Table 5.1 shows the derived parameters for both planets. We note that even if the masses are similar, the model suggests different compositions. This is due to the difference in radii, which is higher for planet c than for planet b. Figure 5.1 suggests that K2-106 b has a composition made of a mixture of rocks and iron (50% of iron and 50% of rocks) consistent with a solid planet with an Earth core. This result agrees with Huang & Ji (2020) and Dai et al. (2021) conclusions that most USP planets have Earth-like compositions and are below $10 M_{\oplus}$ and $10 R_{\oplus}$. Moreover, K2-106 b orbits a star with solar-like metallicity ($[Fe/H] = 0.06 \pm 0.03$), which is another characteristic of USP planets according to the literature (see e.g. Winn et al., 2018; Sanchis-Ojeda et al., 2014). Our results for the composition of K2-106 b, is in agreement with the ones of Guenther et al. (2017) and Simukoff et al. (2017). On the other hand, the composition of K2-106 c seems inconsistent with the models made by Zeng et al. (2016). This is because of the larger radius of K2-106 c. Since K2-106 c is farther away from the host star than the USP, this might imply that this planet have a more extended envelope than K2-106 b. This characteristic could be consistent with the photo-evaporation model. According to Lundkvist et al. (2016), when a small planet ($< 4R_{\oplus}$) receives an insolation $> 650F_{\oplus}$, a gas-rich planet could lose its atmosphere due to photo-evaporation. We note that the insolation received by K2-106 b is $\sim 4694F_{\oplus}$, while the insolation received by K2-106 c is $\sim 70F_{\oplus}$. Therefore, from the point of view of photo-evaporation the difference between the two planets could be consistent with this hypothesis.

Parameter	Value
Stellar Parameters	
Star Mass M_{*} [M_{\odot}]	0.902 ± 0.057
Star Radius R_{*} [R_{\odot}]	0.981 ± 0.019
Effective Temperature T_{eff} [K]	5496 ± 46
Derived parameters of K2-106 b	
Planetary Mass [M_{\oplus}]	$8.02^{+0.91}_{-0.88}$
Planetary Radius [R_{\oplus}]	$1.733^{+0.065}_{-0.06}$
Semi-major axis of the planetary orbit a [AU]	$0.01297^{+0.0007}_{-0.0012}$
Orbit inclination i_p [degrees]	$84.88^{+3.61}_{-6.32}$
Insolation [F_{\oplus}]	4694^{+1043}_{-457}
Equilibrium Temperature T_{eq} [K]	$2303.7^{+118.6}_{-58.3}$
Derived parameters of K2-106 c	
Planetary Mass [M_{\oplus}]	$5.07^{+2.73}_{-2.57}$
Planetary Radius [R_{\oplus}]	$2.923^{+0.106}_{-0.096}$
Semi-major axis of the planetary orbit a [AU]	$0.106^{+0.0057}_{-0.0101}$
Orbit inclination i_p [degrees]	$88.55^{+0.19}_{-0.41}$
Insolation [F_{\oplus}]	$70.33^{+15.63}_{-6.85}$
Equilibrium Temperature T_{eq} [K]	$806.0^{+41.5}_{-20.4}$

Table 5.1: K2-106 system parameters. Stellar parameters were taken from Simukoff et al. (2017) and Dai et al. (2019).

Figure 5.1: Mass-radius diagram for well-characterised (better than 30%) super-Earths and Neptunes. From bottom to top, the solid curves are theoretical models from Zeng et al. (2016) for planets with a composition of 100% iron (brown), 50% silicate and 50% iron (dashed red), 100% silicate (beige), 50% silicate and 50% water (dashed blue), water (light blue). K2-106 b and K2-106 c are highlighted with different symbols and colours.

5.2 Planetary parameters of K2-141

If we combine the results of Tables 4.3 and 4.4 together with stellar parameters given in Barragán et al. (2018b) we are able to estimate the planetary physical parameters of the system. The planetary masses are $5.19^{+0.45}_{-0.45}M_{\oplus}$ for K2-141 b and $5.57^{+2.33}_{-2.26}M_{\oplus}$ for K2-141 c. The radius of K2-141 b is $1.537^{+0.096}_{-0.093}R_{\oplus}$ and the minimum radius of K2-141 c is $1.90R_{\oplus}$. We note that our mass measurements for K2-141 b and K2-141 c are consistent with the masses reported by Barragán et al. (2018b) and Malavolta et al. (2018). More precisely, Malavolta et al. (2018) was the first team to report the detection of K2-141 c. They mentioned that the true mass of K2-141 c has to be $< 7.4M_{\oplus}$. Our mass measurement of K2-141 c, despite its huge error bars, is consistent with the mass limit reported by Malavolta et al. (2018). Our result for K2-141 c's mass is also the first one reported for this system in the scientific literature.

Unlike K2-106, our transit analysis did not give us insights about the stellar parameters of K2-141 reported previously. By using both stellar parameters in our transit fit, the corresponding stellar density is fully consistent with the one obtained from spectroscopy. For this system, transit method and spectroscopy constrain well enough the parameters of the host star.

Table 5.2 shows the derived parameters for both planets K2-141 b and K2-141 c. Like in the analysis of K2-106, we note that even if the masses are similar, the compositions are different. In figure 5.2 a mass-radius diagram with K2-141 b and K2-141 c is shown. In the same Figure the composition models from Zeng et al. (2016) are also displayed. According to our analysis, K2-141 b

has a composition made of rocks and iron (50% of iron and 50% of rocks). This composition, as well as the one of K2-106 b, agrees with [Huang & Ji \(2020\)](#) and [Dai et al. \(2021\)](#) about the rocky, Earth-like composition of USP planets. The composition found for K2-141 b in our analysis is also consistent with the one reported by [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#). K2-141 has a sun-like metallicity ($[Fe/H] = 0.06 \pm 0.20$), so it also agrees with [Huang & Ji \(2020\)](#) regarding that most USP planets do orbit around stars with solar-like metallicity. K2-141 c, on the other hand, cannot be located with precision on the mass-radius diagram since its radius is not measured due to the grazing nature of its transits. The minimum radius for K2-141 c that we can report locates the planet near the composition line of a rocky core with a water or hydrogen envelope. This suggests that K2-141 c could join the group of planets made of rocky cores with an hydrogen envelope like the ones reported by [Chen & Kipping \(2017\)](#). However, we cannot be sure about this. On the other hand, and like in K2-106, the insolation received by K2-141 c is lower than the one that K2-141 b receives. For K2-141 b, the insolation is $\sim 2913F_{\oplus}$ and for K2-141 c is $\sim 34.8F_{\oplus}$. This could support the idea that K2-141 c still hosts a gaseous envelope, despite we cannot know its radius. Finally, in K2-141, the characteristic discussed by [Winn et al. \(2018\)](#) regarding the orbital period ratio of USP planets and their longer-period companions is also fulfilled, as in the case of K2-106 system. The symbol of K2-141 c radius error bar in [Figure Zeng et al. \(2016\)](#) shows that our radius measurement is not conclusive.

Parameter	Value
Stellar Parameters¹	
Star Mass M_* [M_{\odot}]	0.6620 ± 0.0220
Star Radius R_* [R_{\odot}]	0.6740 ± 0.0390
Effective Temperature T_{eff} [K]	4373 ± 57
Derived parameters of K2-141 b	
Planetary Mass [M_{\oplus}]	$5.19^{+0.45}_{-0.45}$
Planetary Radius [R_{\oplus}]	$1.537^{+0.096}_{-0.093}$
Semi-major axis of the planetary orbit a [AU]	$0.00712^{+0.00056}_{-0.00062}$
Orbit inclination i_p [degrees]	$81.47^{+5.69}_{-5.84}$
Insolation [F_{\oplus}]	$2913.0^{+507.0}_{-285.0}$
Equilibrium Temperature T_{eq} [K]	$2044.7^{+83.8}_{-51.9}$
Derived parameters of K2-141 c	
Planetary Mass [M_{\oplus}]	$5.57^{+2.33}_{-2.26}$
Planetary Radius [R_{\oplus}]	$1.90^{(a)}$
Semi-major axis of the planetary orbit a [AU]	$0.0651^{+0.0051}_{-0.0057}$
Orbit inclination i_p [degrees]	$87.21^{+0.15}_{-0.25}$
Insolation [F_{\oplus}]	$34.85^{+6.07}_{-3.40}$
Equilibrium Temperature T_{eq} [K]	$676.3^{+27.7}_{-17.2}$

Table 5.2: K2-141 system parameters. ^(a) Minimum radius allowed from the grazing transit.

¹As presented by [Barragán et al. \(2018b\)](#)

Figure 5.2: Mass-radius diagram for well-characterised (better than 30%) super-Earths and Neptunes. From bottom to top, the solid curves are theoretical models from Zeng et al. (2016) for planets with a composition of 100% iron (brown), 50% silicate and 50% iron (dashed red), 100% silicate (beige), 50 % silicate and 50% water (dashed blue), water (light blue). K2-141 b and K2-141 c are highlighted with different symbols and colours. Since the radius of K2-141 c is an underestimation, the error bar has an arrow that indicates that.

5.3 Planetary parameters of HD 3167

If we combine the results of Tables 4.5 and 4.6 with stellar parameters given in Gandolfi et al. (2017) we are able to estimate the planetary physical parameters of the system. The planetary masses are $5.018 \pm 0.43 M_{\oplus}$ for HD 3167 b and $15.50^{+1.37}_{-1.31} M_{\oplus}$ for HD 3167 c. The radius of HD 3167 b is $1.53^{+0.07}_{-0.06} R_{\oplus}$ and the radius of HD 3167 c is $2.79^{+0.13}_{-0.11} R_{\oplus}$. We note that our mass measurement of HD 3167 b is consistent with the one reported by Gandolfi et al. (2017) and Christiansen et al. (2017). However, for HD 3167 c, our mass measurement does not agree with those reported by these two teams. This difference can be attributed to the stellar activity of HD 3167 and the several RV signals that it induces. A better analysis of the RVs requires a complex periodogram analysis that is out the scope of this thesis.

As for K2-141, our transit analysis did not showed an improvement in the stellar parameters of HD 3167 reported by Gandolfi et al. (2017) and Christiansen et al. (2017). By using both stellar parameters in our transit fit, the correspondent stellar density derived by the modelling of transit light curves is consistent with the one obtained via spectroscopy. For this system, transit method and spectroscopy constrain well enough the parameters of the host star.

Table 5.3 shows the derived parameters for planets HD 3167 b, HD 3167 c and HD 3167 d as well as for the activity-induced RV signals. Like the previous analysis for K2-106 and K2-141, masses and radii of this system are different. In Figure 5.3 a mass-radius diagram with HD 3167 b and HD 3167 c is included. The prediction of the compositions based on the two-layer models of Zeng

et al. (2016) are also shown. According to our analysis, HD 3167 b has a composition consistent with rocks and iron (50% rocky and 50% iron). This composition is pretty similar with the ones obtained for K2-106 b and K2-141 b. Therefore, it also agrees with Huang & Ji (2020) and Dai et al. (2021) about the rocky, Earth-like composition of USP planets. It also agrees with the fact that USP planets tend to move around stars with sun-like metallicity, according to Christiansen et al. (2017), HD 3167 has a metallicity of $[Fe/H] = 0.04 \pm 0.05$. The composition found for HD 3167 b is consistent with the one reported by Gandolfi et al. (2017) and Christiansen et al. (2017), while the composition for HD 3167 c seems to suggest an important amount of pure water (100% water). The reason for this might be the following: since HD 3167 c is bigger than HD 3167 b, HD 3167 c might have a volatile envelope, while HD 3167 b does not. The existence of this envelope around HD 3167 c can be supported taking into account that HD 3167 c is farther away from the host star than HD 3167 b. The insolation of HD 3167 b is $\sim 1674F_{\oplus}$ and the insolation of HD 3167 c is just $\sim 17F_{\oplus}$. This could support the existence of an atmosphere around HD 3167 c. The feature about the orbital period ratio of USP planets and their longer-period companions (see e.g. Winn et al., 2018) also fulfils, as for K2-106 and K2-141.

Parameter	Value
Stellar Parameters²	
Star Mass M_* [M_{\odot}]	$0.877^{+0.024}_{-0.024}$
Star Radius R_* [R_{\odot}]	$0.835^{+0.026}_{-0.026}$
Effective Temperature T_{eff} [K]	5286 ± 40
Derived parameters of HD 3167 b	
Planetary Mass [M_{\oplus}]	$4.98^{+0.43}_{-0.43}$
Planetary Radius [R_{\oplus}]	$1.53^{+0.066}_{-0.06}$
Semi-major axis of the planetary orbit a [AU]	$0.01704^{+0.00095}_{-0.00155}$
Orbit inclination i_p [degrees]	$86.99^{+2.15}_{-3.86}$
Insolation [F_{\oplus}]	$1674.0^{+347.0}_{-138.0}$
Equilibrium Temperature T_{eq} [K]	$1780.4^{+85.8}_{-37.8}$
Derived parameters of HD 3167 c	
Planetary Mass [M_{\oplus}]	$15.54^{+1.32}_{-1.29}$
Planetary Radius [R_{\oplus}]	$2.79^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$
Semi-major axis of the planetary orbit a [AU]	$0.1685^{+0.0093}_{-0.0153}$
Orbit inclination i_p [degrees]	$89.44^{+0.12}_{-0.26}$
Insolation [F_{\oplus}]	$17.12^{+3.55}_{-1.41}$
Equilibrium Temperature T_{eq} [K]	$566.1^{+27.3}_{-12.0}$
Derived parameters of HD 3167 d	
Minimum mass [M_{\oplus}]	$4.68^{+0.86}_{-0.86}$

Table 5.3: HD 3167 system parameters.

²As presented by Gandolfi et al. (2017)

Figure 5.3: Mass-radius diagram for well-characterised (better than 30%) super-Earths and Neptunes. From bottom to top, the solid curves are theoretical models from Zeng et al. (2016) for planets with a composition of 100% iron (brown), 50% silicate and 50% iron (dashed red), 100% silicate (beige), 50 % silicate and 50% water (dashed blue), water (light blue). HD 3167 b and HD 3167 c are highlighted with different symbols and colours.

5.4 General Discussion

In Table 5.4 a detailed description of the planetary parameters of the systems of the thesis can be found. In Figure 5.4 a mass-radius diagram with all the exoplanets of the thesis is displayed, along with Zeng et al. (2016) composition models and all the exoplanets known with a precision better than 30 % as gray circles. The symbol of K2-141 c radius error bar shows that our radius measurement is not a conclusive measurement. In Figure 5.5 a mass-radius diagram for the planets characterised in this thesis is displayed, along with a color code. This color code depends on the planet orbital period. In Figure 5.6 another mass-radius diagram with the planets of this thesis is displayed. In this Figure the color code depends on the planet insolation. If we compare both Figures 5.5 and 5.6 we note that the planets with the shortest orbital periods are those that receive a higher level of stellar irradiation. These planets have the higher density in our sample and are likely bare cores whose atmospheres have been stripped away due to photo-evaporation. On the other hand, planets with longer period and lower irradiation levels, have larger radii. These can be explained by the presence of volatile envelopes, which account for a small fraction of the mass.

Main planetary parameters

Name	$M_p [M_\oplus]$	$R_p [R_\oplus]$	P [days]	a [AU]
K2-106 b	$8.02^{+0.91}_{-0.88}$	$1.733^{+0.065}_{-0.06}$	$0.571294^{+1.5e-05}_{-1.5e-05}$	$0.01297^{+0.0007}_{-0.00124}$
K2-106 c	$5.07^{+2.73}_{-2.57}$	$2.923^{+0.106}_{-0.096}$	$13.33968^{+0.00095}_{-0.00106}$	$0.106^{+0.0057}_{-0.0101}$
K2-141 b	$5.19^{+0.45}_{-0.45}$	$1.543^{+0.093}_{-0.092}$	$0.28032477^{+1.2e-07}_{-1.2e-07}$	$0.00712^{+0.00056}_{-0.00062}$
K2-141 c	$5.57^{+2.33}_{-2.26}$	$1.9^{(a)}$	$7.748449^{+2.3e-05}_{-2.2e-05}$	$0.0651^{+0.0051}_{-0.0057}$
HD 3167 b	$4.98^{+0.43}_{-0.43}$	$1.53^{+0.066}_{-0.06}$	$0.959644^{+2e-05}_{-2e-05}$	$0.01704^{+0.00095}_{-0.00155}$
HD 3167 c	$15.54^{+1.32}_{-1.29}$	$2.79^{+0.12}_{-0.11}$	$29.8468^{+0.0015}_{-0.0014}$	$0.1685^{+0.0093}_{-0.0153}$

 Table 5.4: Main parameters of the planetary systems whose masses and radii have been derived as part of the thesis project here presented. ^(a) Minimum radius allowed from the grazing transit.

Figure 5.4: Mass-radius diagram for all the exoplanets of this thesis project. The gray squares represent exoplanets whose masses and radii are known with a precision better than 30 %. The coloured circles mark the exoplanets that have been characterised in the course of this thesis work (See Table 5.4). Each planet is represented with a different color. K2-141 b has an arrow indicating that the reported radius is an underestimation of the real radius. In the figure, Zeng et al. (2016) composition models are also shown.

Figure 5.5: Mass-radius diagram for all the exoplanets of this thesis project. The coloured circles mark the exoplanets that have been characterised in the course of this thesis work (See Table 5.4). The color code represents the orbital period of each planet in Earth days. In the figure, Zeng et al. (2016) composition models are also shown.

Figure 5.6: Mass-radius diagram for all the exoplanets of this thesis project. The coloured circles mark the exoplanets that have been characterised in the course of this thesis work (See Table 5.4). The color code represents the insolation received by each planet in terms of F_{\oplus} (Earth insolation). In the figure, Zeng et al. (2016) composition models are also shown.

During this thesis we have studied small USP planets ($R_p < 1.7R_{\oplus}$ and $P < 1$ Earth day) and our knowledge about them has vastly increased. However, USPs have been studied since *Kepler* space mission. For instance, it is well known that almost all USP planets does belong to multi-planet systems (see e.g. Sanchis-Ojeda et al., 2014; Huang & Ji, 2020). As an exception, only three USP planets does seem to be alone in their systems. They are: K2-131, Kepler-78 and K2-291. Nevertheless, it seems that these systems are heavily contaminated by activity-induced RV variations that might overshadow outer planetary companions (see Dai et al., 2021). However, and as expected, the three USP planets of this thesis have planetary companions. They also have compositions and properties indicating that photo-evaporation may indeed play a role in understanding the diversity of multi-planet systems and the formation of the radius gap for small planets (Fulton et al., 2017).

Our results confirm as well that small planets with similar masses can have different radii. For instance, the three USP planets studied in this thesis likely have rocky-iron compositions. On the other hand, their outer and longer-period planetary companions tend to have compositions that might involve water or hydrogen envelopes with a rocky core. This comes into account regarding the fact that orbital period ratios between adjacent longer-period planets and USP planets are almost always greater than 3 (Winn et al., 2018). This is remarkable since for multi-planet systems in general the planetary period ratios between adjacent orbits are within the range of 1.5–4, according to Fabrycky et al. (2014). For the systems of our thesis, we found that K2-106’s period ratio is ~ 23 , for K2-141 ~ 27.6 and for HD 3167 ~ 31.1 . This is consistent with the feature described by Winn et al. (2018).

K2-141 is a multi-planet system that deserves a particular comment about it. K2-141 b is a small USP planet with a terrestrial composition, mostly rocks and iron. On the other hand, K2-141 c minimum radius locates the planet near a [Zeng et al. \(2016\)](#) composition model consistent with a rocky core with a water envelope. Nevertheless, since K2-141 c's transits are grazing, we cannot be sure of its radius. The best we can do for this planet is to report the minimum radius of $R_p = 1.90R_\oplus$. This is the value of the 1 % of the posterior distribution for this parameter. However, the mass of K2-141 c has not been determined previously in the literature. There are several reasons for this. The first reason is that the RV signal of K2-141 c might be simply too small ($K_c = 2.39_{-0.97}^{+0.99} m s^{-1}$). The second reason has something to do with the orbital period of K2-141 c. According to [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#), K2-141 c's orbital period is close to the first harmonic of the rotational period of the star, and this may lead to problems in disentangling the planetary and stellar signals. Therefore, a better modelling of the stellar induced RV signal may lead to a better detection of K2-141 c signal. With the result obtained in this thesis, we showed that by combining the [Barragán et al. \(2018a\)](#) and [Malavolta et al. \(2018\)](#) RV data sets, we are close to measure the mass of K2-141 c. In fact, following the results in this thesis, we performed a more robust approach to model the stellar signal in the RVs and we were able to get a > 3 sigma detection of K2-141 c. The analysis of *K2* campaign 19 presented here, together with the mass measurement of K2-141 c will be reported in a peer-reviewed manuscript (Gutiérrez-Canales et al., in prep.).

Chapter 6

Conclusions

There are more things in Heaven
and Earth, Horatio, that are
dreamt of in your philosophy.

William Shakespeare, Hamlet.

6.1 Summary and Conclusions

In this thesis, we carried out a multi-planet analysis of several transiting exoplanets detected by the *K2* space mission that were later the targets of intensive follow-up RV observations. We carried out the analysis with the scientific code `pyaneti` and we derived planetary masses, radii and densities of the following systems:

- **K2-106** is a transiting multi-planet system hosting an USP planet ($P = 0.57$ days) which is a super-Earth with a mass of $8.02_{-0.88}^{+0.91} M_{\oplus}$ and a radius of $1.733_{-0.06}^{+0.065} R_{\oplus}$. K2-106 b has a rocky-iron composition. On the other hand, K2-106 c ($P = 13.3$ days) has a mass of $5.07_{-2.57}^{+2.73} M_{\oplus}$ and a radius of $2.923_{-0.096}^{+0.106} R_{\oplus}$. K2-106 c's composition does not agree with the composition models reported by [Zeng et al. \(2016\)](#), suggesting that a two-layer composition model does not fit with this planet.
- **K2-141** is a transiting multi-planet system hosting an USP planet ($P = 0.28$ days) which is a super-Earth with a mass of $5.19_{-0.45}^{+0.45} M_{\oplus}$ and a radius of $1.543_{-0.092}^{+0.093} R_{\oplus}$. K2-141 b has a rocky-iron composition. On the other hand, K2-141 c ($P = 7.74$ days) has a mass of $5.57_{-2.26}^{+2.33} M_{\oplus}$ and a minimum radius of $1.90 R_{\oplus}$ that does not allow us to locate K2-141 c near a certain composition model with confidence. This is the first reported measurement of the mass of K2-141 c.
- **HD 3167** is a transiting multi-planet system hosting an USP planet ($P = 0.95$ days) which is a super-Earth with a mass of $4.98_{-0.43}^{+0.43} M_{\oplus}$ and a radius of $1.53_{-0.06}^{+0.066} R_{\oplus}$. HD 3167 b has a rocky-iron composition. On the other hand, HD 3167 c ($P = 29.8$ days) has a mass of $15.54_{-1.29}^{+1.32} M_{\oplus}$ and a radius of $2.79_{-0.11}^{+0.12} R_{\oplus}$. HD 3167 c lies near the water-composition line. Nevertheless, this does not mean that HD 3167 c has a water composition. That would be a very strong assertion. A more cautious interpretation would be a rocky core with a thick volatile envelope made of hydrogen. On the other hand, HD 3167 d is a non-transiting exoplanet according to [Christiansen et al. \(2017\)](#). We found a minimum mass of $4.68_{-0.86}^{+0.86} M_{\oplus}$.

6.2 Perspectives and Future work

USP planets consist in one of the most interesting type of planets known to date. Studying them offer a possibility to understand how photo-evaporation shape exoplanets and might contribute to create the radius-gap. However, there are still important questions that have to be addressed, for instance, how can we explain the very small percentage of Hot-Jupiters that are in fact USP planets? How can we constrain the origin of USP planets inside a multi-planet system? What are the physical mechanisms driving their evolution? Planetary migration has something to do with all this?

More and more planets are being discovered every year. Space missions such as *Kepler*, *K2* and instruments like HARPS and HARPS-N have helped us to understand the existence and nature of exoplanets. These space-based transiting missions and spectrographs were a revolution for the exoplanets research community and marked the beginning of a new era for this field. Currently, *TESS* space mission is studying the brightest dwarfs stars in our galaxy and it is producing a torrent of high-quality observations and valuable data about exoplanets in an unprecedented way. Moreover all this, the future for exoplanet community is very promising. For instance, if we take into account that future space-based transiting missions like *PLATO* and *ARIEL*, even *JWST* to be launched next year, will help us to improve our knowledge about exoplanets and possible Earth-like candidates drastically. Also, the next generation of ground-based telescopes and high-precision spectrographs will help us to better constrain the origin of these systems and the physical mechanism driving their evolution.

Appendix A

TOI-451

During the writing of my thesis I gained a lot of experience and knowledge regarding data analysis and scientific programming with `pyaneti`. This knowledge allowed me to participate on a Research Note of the American Astronomical Society about the multi-planet system TOI-451 ([Barragán et al., 2021](#)). My contribution to the Research Note was to perform the model of the three transiting exoplanets of the system. Since Research Notes are typically short papers with just one or none figures at all, we attached in the following pages the Research Note as it is presented in [arxiv](#).

TESS re-observes the young multi-planet system TOI-451: refined ephemeris and activity evolution

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ABSTRACT

We present a new analysis of the light curve of the young planet-hosting star TOI 451 in the light of new observations from *TESS* Cycle 3. Our joint analysis of the transits of all three planets, using all available *TESS* data, results in an improved ephemeris for TOI 451 b and TOI 451 c, which will help to plan follow-up observations. The updated mid-transit times are $\text{BJD} - 2,457,000 = 1410.9896^{+0.0032}_{-0.0029}$, $1411.7982^{+0.0022}_{-0.0020}$, and $1416.63407^{+0.00096}_{-0.00100}$ for TOI 451 b, c, and d, respectively, and the periods are $1.8587028^{+08e-06}_{-10e-06}$, $9.192453^{+4.1e-05}_{-3.3e-05}$, and $16.364932^{+3.6e-05}_{-3.5e-05}$ days. We also model the out-of-transit light curve using a Gaussian Process with a quasi-periodic kernel, and infer a change in the properties of the active regions on the surface of TOI 451 between *TESS* Cycles 1 and 3.

Keywords: Exoplanets (498); Stellar activity (1580); Transits (1711)

Using data collected by NASA’s Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (*TESS*; Ricker et al. 2015) during its first year of operations, combined with ground-based follow-up observations, Newton et al. (2021, hereafter N21) discovered a system of three transiting planets orbiting the star TOI 451, a member of the young (120 Myr) Pisces–Eridanus stream. As the host star is relatively bright ($V = 11.02$), it is amenable to further follow-up, including Radial Velocity (RV) observations to measure the planetary masses, and transmission spectroscopy to characterise the planets’ atmospheres. Further characterisation of a system like TOI 451 is expected to provide valuable constraints for models of planet formation and early evolution, but depends critically on our ability to predict the times of future transits accurately, and model the signals arising from active regions on the star’s surface, which are important for both RV data and transmission spectra.

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TESS first observed TOI 451 (TIC 257605131) in Cycle 1 during sectors 4 and 5 (from 2018-Oct-18 to 2018-Dec-11). These observations, together with additional ground- and space-based photometry, were used by N21 to discover and validate the three transiting planets which are known around TOI 451 to date. Two years later, *TESS* re-visited TOI 451 in its extended mission during its Cycle 3 in sector 31 (from 2020-Oct-21 to 2020-Nov-19). In this Note we analyse the *TESS* data from Cycles 1 and 3 jointly.

We downloaded the *TESS* light curves for the three sectors from the [Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes](#). We use the Pre-search Data Conditioning Simple Aperture Photometry (PDC SAP) light curve as the starting point for our analysis. This light curve is corrected for known instrumental effects at the pixel level, as well as for common-mode systematics.

Before modelling the transits, we detrend the light curve with `citlalicue`, which uses a quasi-periodic Gaussian Process (GP) implemented in `george` (Ambikasaran et al. 2015) to model the activity-induced variability in the out-of-transit data, together with `pytransit` (Parviainen 2015) to predict the times at which transits occur. We mask out all the transits when fitting the GP, and remove other outliers by clipping at ± 5 -sigma. We then divide by the GP model to obtain a detrended light curve containing transits only. Because the Cycle 1 and 3 observations were taken two years apart, we detrended them separately. Figure 1 shows the PDC SAP light curve, together with the GP model, and the detrended light curve, phase-folded at the period of each planet and zoomed in on the transits. We return to the GP model at the end of this note when discussing activity.

We then extracted sections of the detrended light curve around each transit, and modelled them using `pyaneti` (Barragán et al. 2019). We model the transits of all a three planets simultaneously, assuming circular orbits. For each planet, we vary the time of mid-transit T_0 , orbital period P , impact parameter b , and scaled planet radius, R_p/R_\star . We also vary the stellar density, and convert it to scaled semi-major axis for each planet using Kepler’s third law. Finally, we model for the stellar limb darkening following a quadratic limb darkening model. We used wide uniform priors for all the parameters. This results in the following estimates for the planet parameters (b, c, and d respectively on each line):

- $T_0(\text{BJD} - 2\,457\,000) = 1410.9896^{+0.0032}_{-0.0029}$, $1411.7982^{+0.0022}_{-0.0020}$, $1416.63407^{+0.00096}_{-0.00100}$;
- $P(\text{days}) = 1.8587028^{+08e-06}_{-10e-06}$, $9.192453^{+4.1e-05}_{-3.3e-05}$, $16.364932^{+3.6e-05}_{-3.5e-05}$;
- $R_p/R_\star = 0.01974 \pm 0.00068$, $0.03217^{+0.00083}_{-0.00086}$, $0.04296^{+0.00080}_{-0.00078}$;
- $R_p(R_\oplus) = 1.892^{+0.096}_{-0.094}$, 3.08 ± 0.14 , 4.12 ± 0.17 .

where we converted from R_p/R_\star to R_p using the stellar radius of $0.879 \pm 0.032 R_\odot$ given by N21.

All our estimates are consistent with the values reported by N21, but our ephemeris for planets b and c are significantly improved, by a factor ~ 3 and ~ 2 , respectively. We do not improve on the ephemeris for TOI 451 d as Sector 31 includes only two new transits of this planet, and N21 combined data from *TESS* Sector 4 and 5 with five additional transits observed with other facilities, which we do not analyse here. The best-fit transit model for each planet is shown in the bottom row of Figure 1.

As expected for such a young star, TOI 451 is active, and displays significant out-of-transit variability due to the rotational modulation and evolution of the active regions on the stellar surface,

Figure 1. Top panel: PDC-SAP light curve (grey) along with best-fit GP+transit model (red), for *TESS* sectors 4 & 5. Also shown, with a vertical offset for clarity, are the detrended light curve (blue) and the transit-only model (orange). Middle panel: same as top panel, but for sector 31. Bottom row: detrended light curves phase-folded at the period of each planet (individual data points in grey, phase-binned data in red) together with the best-fit transit model (black line), with the residuals in the lower inset.

which is clearly visible in the top panel of Figure 1. It is interesting to note that this variability looks qualitatively different in *TESS* Cycle 1 and 3. Compared to sectors 4 & 5, the stellar variability in sector 31 has a larger amplitude and appears to be more coherent. Cycle 1 also showed hints of a

‘beat pattern’, which is not seen in sector 31. Such beat patterns can arise when two or more active regions are present on the stellar surface, and evolve or rotate at different rates.

To quantify these differences, we explore the range of parameters of our quasi-periodic GP model which are compatible with the data in each Cycle. To speed up this process, since we are only interested variations on timescales of a day or more, we binned the data in 6 hour bins. We used `pyaneti` to model the light curves using a GP with the Quasi-Periodic kernel:

$$\gamma_{\text{QP}}(t_i, t_j) = A^2 \exp \left[-\frac{\sin^2 [\pi (t_i - t_j) / P_{\text{GP}}] - \frac{(t_i - t_j)^2}{2\lambda_e^2}}{2\lambda_p^2} \right], \quad (1)$$

where P_{GP} is the period of the activity signal, λ_p is the length scale of the periodic component, and λ_e is the long term evolution timescale. While P_{GP} and λ_e have units of days, λ_p is dimensionless.

The results of this analysis are as follows (each line reports the value for sectors 4 & 5 first, then the value for sector 31):

- $A = 2.8_{-0.3}^{+0.4} \times 10^{-3}, 9.8_{-1.9}^{+2.5} \times 10^{-3},$
- $\lambda_e(\text{days}) = 4.93_{-0.32}^{+0.33}, 8.17_{-0.72}^{+0.80},$
- $\lambda_p = 0.359_{-0.022}^{+0.025}, 0.699_{-0.093}^{+0.136}$
- $P_{\text{GP}}(\text{days}) = 5.127_{-0.056}^{+0.064}, 5.184_{-0.058}^{+0.052}.$

As expected, the GP period is consistent between both analyses, and they agree with the stellar rotation period derived by N21. However, the remaining hyper-parameters are not consistent between the two data sets. Specifically, the GP amplitude A , the evolutionary time-scale λ_e , and the periodic length scale λ_p are all significantly larger in *TESS* Cycle 3 than in Cycle 1. This confirms our qualitative visual assessment of the light curve, and indicates that the size and distribution of the active regions has evolved significantly during the two years separating the two sets of observations.

This may prove important when planning future follow-up observations of the target. In particular, we recommend attempting to obtain photometric monitoring contemporaneous with any future spectroscopic observations, and/or explicitly using activity indicators extracted from the spectra themselves to disentangle between stellar and planetary signals (e.g., [Rajpaul et al. 2015](#); [Barragán et al. 2019](#)). Relying on the light curves from previous seasons to constrain the lifetime and distribution of the active regions on the stellar surface may not be appropriate for this target.

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